

Excellent peripheries for a strong
European Research Area

D4.2 Capacity Building Plan and report on capacity building activities

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Acronyms & Abbreviations

CBAs	Capacity Building Activities
CBP	Capacity Building Plan
CBNs	Capacity Building Needs
CLAB	Contamination Laboratories
CIDE	Spanish acronym for “Innovation and Business Development Centers”
D	Deliverable
EC	European Commission
EIC	European Innovation Council
ERC	European Research Council
EU	European Union
HEIs	Higher Education Institutions
ICT	Information and communications technology
IP	Intellectual Property

IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
ICEX	Spanish acronym for “Spanish Institute of Foreign Trade”
InUAC	Technology-based Incubator of UAc
IT	Information Technology
KIT	Karlsruhe Institute of Technology
KTT	Knowledge and Technology Transfer
OPE	Spanish acronym for “European Projects Office”
OPII	Spanish acronym for “Industrial and Intellectual Property Office”
ORs	Outermost regions
OTC	Spanish acronym for “Knowledge Transfer Office”
ProCIED	Pro-Rectorate for Cooperation, Internationalisation and Distance Learning of UAc
SCWGs	Societal challenges working groups
SVCT	Science and Technology Service department of UAc
TPTRS	Training Plan for Teachers and Research Staff
UAc	University of the Azores
UAI	Spanish acronym for “Research support unit” of the ULPGC Library
ULPGC	University of Las Palmas de Gran Canaria
VReAPI	Vice-Rectorate for Administration, Planning and Infrastructures of UAc
VReBECEI	Vice-Rectorate for Students, Well-being and Institutional of UAc
VReEGA	Vice-Rectorate for Education and Academic Affairs of UAc
VReCITC	Vice-Rectorate for Science, Innovation and Knowledge Transfer of UAc
VRRT	Vice-Rectorate for Research and Transfer of ULPGC
VRTAE	Vice-Rectorate of Teaching Staff, Academic Planning and Educational Innovation
WP	Work Package

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Under the umbrella of the Horizon Europe Programme, the EXPER project aims to significantly enhance and boost the capacity building skills of the staff and the surrounding ecosystems of the University of Las Palmas de Gran Canaria (ULPGC) and the University of the Azores (UAc). This initiative is aligned with the strategic goals of the European Union in Higher Education, Research and Innovation, aiming to foster competency development and capacity building within these Higher Academic Institutions (HEIs), including the relevant actors and stakeholders that constitute the quadruple helix model (companies, citizens, knowledge centres and public administration).

The need for this report stems from the challenges and barriers faced by outermost regions (ORs). The H2020 FORWARD project, in which UAc and ULPGC became crucial actors, was funded to facilitate networking and collaboration among Research and Innovation Ecosystems in ORs, and to support researchers and research organizations from these areas in their efforts to participate in EU-funded and other international research projects. However, results from FORWARD project showed that further efforts are necessary to ensure a transformation at the institutional level for universities in ORs to modernize their structures and enhance their research and innovation outputs. In this respect, the capacity building competences of the community becomes a key driver factor.

The organization of supporting and capacity building activities on how to increase research excellence and unlock the innovation potential of Widening Universities, with a focus on knowledge transfer, is one of the principal goals of the EXPER project. As a result of WP1 (Regional ecosystems assessment and cooperation models) & WP2 (Co-designing modernization with surrounding ecosystems), for the assessment of the regional ecosystems of the Canary Islands and the Azores and the implementation of the modernization strategies of ULPGC and UAc, respectively, both entities have identified clear needs to improve their relationships with their surrounding ecosystems. These relationships will be enhanced and strengthened through interviews, capacity building activities, staff exchanges, workshops, focus groups, webinars and other type of public events like conferences and informative events. In other words, the EXPER project becomes a common thread for the sustainable and inclusive growth of the ORs and the well-being of their inhabitants, introducing a tangible and measurable added value.

Should it be recalled that one of the most relevant goals of EXPER project is to support the institutional transformation of ULPGC and UAc through capacity building activities, mutual learning and joint research activities, facilitated by strong cooperation with leading universities such as Rostock University (UROS) and the University of Calabria (UNICAL).

1. INTRODUCTION

The D.4.2: "Capacity Building Plan and Report on Capacity Building Activities" is integrated into WP4 – Promoting Excellent and Responsible Research. WP4 focuses on enhancing research and innovation capacities through strategic initiatives, aligning with the goals of the CBP, which aims to improve research management skills and foster responsible research practices across the EXPER universities.

This deliverable is particularly relevant to Task 4.3. Transversal skills for excellent and responsible research, which involves designing and delivering a capacity building plan that addresses key skills in research management, Open Science practices, research data management, and responsible research. Specifically, the plan will include training on Open Science practices, research data management in Horizon Europe projects, responsible research, and scientific education to foster the use of Horizon Europe research results in education. Additionally, the plan will cover training related to KTT, entrepreneurship and preparation of project proposals to secure funding within the framework of European Union Programs. By equipping researchers with these skills, the project supports the formation and effectiveness of multidisciplinary research groups and the preparation of competitive research proposals to be funded by the Horizon Europe Programme.

Additionally, the CBP supports Task 4.1. Establishment and coordination of “societal challenges working groups”, which involves establishing Societal Challenges Working Groups (SCWGs) consisting of researchers, entrepreneurs, and representatives from relevant organizations. These groups benefit from enhanced research management skills and responsible research practices, enabling them to effectively plan and deliver multidisciplinary research projects addressing societal challenges in the ORs. The SCWGs will be provided with logistical support and advice for developing Horizon Europe projects and establishing strong networks in new research strands.

Overall, the CBP is integral to WP4 as it enhances the foundational skills and knowledge required for excellent and responsible research. This ensures that the EXPER universities can effectively collaborate, innovate, and create a positive societal impact, aligning with the broader objectives of the project.

1.1. PURPOSE OF THE DOCUMENT

The present document: D.4.2 “Capacity Building Plan (CBP) and report on capacity building activities” is a key deliverable that details the capacity building activities undertaken and planned at these universities, framed around the three main thematic pillars of the EXPER project and related WPs (3, 4 and 5), and its expected outcomes in terms of capacity development:

Pillar 1: Attracting and Retaining Talent (WP3).

- 🌐 Description of implemented and planned strategies to attract academic and student talent to both universities.
- 🌐 Initiatives to retain talented professionals and students, including professional development programs, incentives, and improvements in working and academic conditions.

Pillar 2: Excellent and Responsible Research (WP4).

- 🌐 Details of activities conducted and planned to promote scientific excellence, including research programs and training in ethics and responsible research practices.
- 🌐 Evaluation of the results achieved and the expected impacts on the quality of research and innovation within the universities.

Pillar 3: Knowledge and Technology Transfer (KTT) and Connection with Businesses (WP5).

- 🌐 Inventory of knowledge and technology transfer activities, including collaborations with industry, creation of spin-offs, and patents.
- 🌐 Previous, present and forthcoming plans to strengthen links between the universities and the business sector, promoting innovation and economic development through effective collaboration.

This document is aimed and intended to be a useful tool for a diverse audience, both within the university community and outside it (surrounding ecosystem). In particular, to the following profiles:

- 🌐 University students: To understand the opportunities and strategies in place for attracting and retaining their talent, as well as to benefit from the enhanced research and innovation environment.
- 🌐 Researchers & Professors: To gain insights into the efforts being made to promote excellent and responsible research, and to engage with the capacity building activities that enhance their research capabilities and impact.
- 🌐 Project Managers and Knowledge Transfer Officers: To utilize the strategies and plans detailed in the document for preparing and managing successful European projects and facilitating effective KTT.
- 🌐 Entrepreneurs: To explore the initiatives related to KTT, and to discover ways to collaborate with the universities and boosting their business opportunities.

In conclusion, the D.4.2: "Capacity Building Plan and Report on Capacity Building Activities" is not only a tool for accountability and monitoring of actions undertaken within the framework of the EXPER project, but also intended to serve as a future strategic guide for ULPGC and UAc in their ongoing and future efforts to enhance their capacities and meaningfully contribute to the scientific, technological, and socio-economic development of their regions. This report reflects the commitment of both institutions to excellence, responsibility and collaboration, which are fundamental pillars for their future success and relevance in the academic and business landscape within the European Union.

1.2. STRUCTURE OF THE DOCUMENT

This deliverable has the following content and structure:

- Capacity Building requirements identified in previous Exper Project implementation stages (section 2).
- CBAs already implemented in the Widening Universities (section 3).
- CBPs (section 4).
- Impact and Communication Activities (section 5).
- Report on CBAs (section 6).
- Conclusions (section 7).
- Annex (section 8).

2. CAPACITY BUILDING REQUIREMENTS IDENTIFIED IN PREVIOUS EXPER PROJECT IMPLEMENTATION STAGES

This section outlines the capacity building needs (CBNs) identified in earlier stages of the EXPER project. It begins with a detailed account of the CBNs detected on the initial assessments of ULPGC and UAc (conducted within the framework of the tasks 1.2.

Widening University Assessment, and 1.3. Assessment of surrounding ecosystems). Following this subsection, the best practices recommendations from leading universities (UROS and UNICAL) are highlighted. Finally, the strategic objectives and capacity building actions planned, as defined in D2.2 Action Plans developed, for both universities, are summarized. This comprehensive overview ensures targeted capacity building efforts, leveraging best practices to enhance the universities' roles in regional development and innovation.

2.1. UAC CAPACITY BUILDING NEEDS

2.1.1 NEEDS BASED ON THE WIDENING UNIVERSITIES ASSESSMENT

In this sub-section, the CBNs detected during the initial assessments of the UAc are presented (see Table 1. CBNs identified in the UAc's assessment and in the assessment of its surrounding ecosystem under WP1.). These assessments, conducted under Task 1.2 and Task 1.3 of WP1 (previously mentioned in this report), highlighted critical areas where certain training and capacity building activities are considered essential to overcome some of the institutional and regional barriers identified.

Table 1. CBNs identified in the UAc's assessment and in the assessment of its surrounding ecosystem under WP1.

WP	Aspect	Barrier	CBN
Attracting and retaining talents (WP3)	Career development opportunities	No additional training opportunities at their respective institutions	To offer opportunities for professional growth such as training, workshops, or further education. Encourage and support participation in these activities.
	Ethical excellence	Ethics training programs	To develop regular <i>training programs</i> on <i>ethical standards</i> for both research staff and students.
		Ethical awareness and understanding	To cultivate a comprehensive understanding of the university's ethical guidelines and the function of the Ethics Committee: through periodic newsletters, emails, or updates regarding ethical policies and committee activities.
Promoting Excellent and Responsible Research (WP4)	Education capacities	Communication and collaboration: insufficient internal communication within the institution and a perceived lack of collaboration	To develop comprehensive communication strategies to keep faculty, researchers, teachers and students informed about the university's initiatives.
		Promotion of excellence research activities	To establish a dedicated public relations or communications team responsible for showcasing research achievements, both internally and externally.

	Advanced Research Production	Interdisciplinarity: current advanced research activities remain restricted to traditional divisions in the branch of sciences	Acquisition of new skills for researchers and fostering strategies to step them outside their comfort zones. To facilitate and encourage research centres to host specialists from different scientific fields.
Connection with business environment: knowledge transfer and spinoffs (WP5)	KTT Strategies and organizations	Uncertainty about KTT	To strengthen KTT Literacy, implementing, training programs, seminars, and workshops for staff members and researchers. This will help build a comprehensive understanding of KTT processes, importance, and benefits.
		KTT resources	To Identify the resource needs of KTT. securing additional funding, hiring or training skilled personnel, and efficiently utilizing existing resources. Seek out public, private, and governmental funding opportunities, grants, and partnerships.
	Start-Up support and incubation	Provision and communication of start-up support and incubation services	To offer entrepreneurship training and workshops would help to equip students, faculty, and alumni with the necessary skills for business start-up and development.
		Lack of awareness within the university community regarding start-ups and spin-offs.	To organize awareness campaigns, workshops, and seminars on entrepreneurship and the benefits of start-up support.

2.1.2 IDENTIFICATION OF BEST PRACTICES

In the context of the EXPER project, the identification and implementation of best practices from leading universities (UROS and UNICAL) are crucial for enhancing the research and innovation capacities of ULPGC and UAc. Task 1.4. Good Practices from

Leading Universities of the WP1 was specifically designed to address this need by leveraging the successful models employed at partner institutions like the University of Rostock (UROS).

A primary action under Task 1.4 was the creation of a comprehensive catalogue of good practices at UROS. This catalogue provided a detailed representation of the existing structures, services, and activities that support research and innovation (R&I) at UROS. The main objective was to offer a foundational resource for making informed decisions regarding the development and implementation of structural improvements at ULPGC and UAc.

Subsequently, three workshops were organized in collaboration with UROS, engaging all EXPER partners and their communities. Each workshop focused on one of the three specific goals of the project:

- **Attractiveness of Researcher's Careers:** This session focused on strategies to enhance the appeal of research careers, addressing the challenge of attracting and retaining top talent in the academic and research sectors.
- **Excellent and Responsible Research:** This workshop aimed to disseminate knowledge on high-quality and ethically sound research practices, helping to foster a culture of excellence and responsibility within the universities.
- **Enhanced KTT for a broader Public-Private Cooperation:** The third workshop explored ways to strengthen collaboration between academia and industry, emphasizing the importance of public-private partnerships in driving innovation and regional development.

The critical outcome of these workshops was the formulation of a recommendation plan. This plan synthesized the insights and recommendations generated during the workshops into actionable strategies. It aimed to provide valuable input for the development of the EXPER strategy and action plans under WP2.

Therefore, the purpose of this section is to extract the information gathered from Task 1.4. and present the identified CBNs and related activities. By aligning these recommendations with the broader strategic goals of the EXPER project, the CBP will serve as a roadmap for implementing effective changes. This approach ensures that ULPGC and UAc can enhance their research and innovation landscapes, ultimately contributing to regional development and competitiveness.

In conclusion, through the implementation of Task 1.4, the following CBNs were identified at UAc.

Table 2. CBNs identified at UAc through the implementation of Task 1.4., following the Best Practice Catalogue from UROS.

WP	Identification of Best Practice (UROS) ¹	CBN
Attracting and retaining talents (WP3)	Didactic certificate	Implementation of didactic training to gain new competences in teaching
	Diversity Office	Cultural Awareness Workshops
	Female Mentoring	Skill-Building Workshops for females
	Online Learning Platform	Training and skills updating platform for employees
Promoting Excellent and Responsible Research (WP4)	Communication	Staff Training on IT Communication
	Scientific Qualification Courses	Scientific calls and programs workshops, advance research methods, project management, how-to-publish workshops, IPR workshops
	Partnerships (Research)	Promoting R&D staff mobility and training
Connection with business environment: knowledge transfer and spinoffs (WP5)	Careers Service	Training in specific skills demanded by companies
	KTT Office	KTT Education and training programs
	Partnerships between Chairs and Industry	To promote Industrial PhD programs
	Patent and Standards Centre	Training on IP protection
	Start-Up and Entrepreneurship Centre	Practical training and Industry relations Seminars in University Teaching

2.1.3 STRATEGIC OBJECTIVES & CAPACITY BUILDING ACTIONS PLANNED

The Action Plan for UAc, developed in the framework of the EXPER project, is a pivotal component for advancing the institution's capabilities in research, innovation, and academia-business cooperation. This plan, detailed in D2.2. Action Plans developed, builds on the results of the comprehensive assessments carried out in WP1 (Regional ecosystems assessment and cooperation models). These assessments identified key barriers, but also opportunities at institutional, regional, and national levels that could impact the university's role as a driver of regional development and competitiveness.

The Action Plan falls under the scope of WP2 (Co-designing modernization with surrounding ecosystems) and specifically under Task 2.4 Developing Action Plans. The D2.2. Action Plans developed, which was the key outcome related to Task 2.4, aimed to

¹ For further information and details on the best practices, please consult the Best Practice Catalogue from UROS at the last section of this report (Section 8. Annex).

outline a concrete set of actions for ULPGC and UAc, based on the strategic objectives defined through a collaborative co-design methodology. This methodology engaged stakeholders in establishing a vision and mission for each Widening University, culminating in the creation of both individual and joint strategies.

The Individual Strategy for UAc, as well as the Joint Strategy between ULPGC and UAc, were designed to address the three main lines of action in EXPER project: excellent and responsible research, attraction and retention of talent, and knowledge transfer and cooperation with surrounding ecosystems. The strategic objectives set forth in these strategies are aimed at overcoming identified weaknesses and leveraging opportunities to enhance the universities' roles in their respective regions.

In this section, we present a summary of the strategic objectives and the specific actions planned to address CBNs. These actions are derived from both the Individual Strategy for UAc and the Joint Strategy between ULPGC and UAc, focusing on activities related to training and capacity building. The table below outlines these strategic objectives and the associated Capacity Building Actions.

Table 3. Capacity Building Actions Planned set forth in D2.2. Actions Plans Developed (UAc)

Strategic Objective (SO)	Capacity Building Action Planned
SO1: Foster applied research, interdisciplinarity and internationalization	A1.2. Preparation of joint research projects under European funded calls (through proposal writing training workshops)
	A1.4. Participate in international workshops to develop transversal scientific skills (Open Science, Data Management, Responsible Research, Science Communication, etc)
	A.5. Improving the dissemination of research results between Widening Universities (UAc/ULPGC) and entrepreneurial/business ecosystem in both regions.
	A.6. Developing a summer-school
SO2. Promote a culture of innovation and technology transfer	A.2. Implementing the CLAB model in Widening Universities
	A2.2. Promote training of teaching and research staff in various skills to enhance their performance in technology transfer activities
	A2.4. Promote dynamics that can create value, based on the knowledge produced at the University, transforming the research outputs in social and economic value, through InUAc support services for pre-incubation, incubation, and post-incubation purposes, increasing the number of incubated projects and spinoffs creation.
SO3. Invest in a people-centric University	A3.6. Foster gender equality and promote diversity, by formulating a diverse strategy (also organizing raising awareness and communication activities)
SO4. Stimulate cooperation, external communication and social connection	A4.4. Maintain and increase the current student mobility through the Erasmus+, Euroeudisseia and other programs.
	A4.5. Maintain and increase the current academic staff mobility (teaching and training assignments).
	A.10. Promote informative-educational activities in primary and secondary schools in both ORs, with the aim of bringing research and science closer to the new generations and fostering their critical and creative thinking.

By implementing these actions, UAc aims to enhance its institutional capabilities, foster a culture of excellence and responsibility in research, and strengthen its connections with the business sector and broader community.

2.2. ULPGC CAPACITY BUILDING NEEDS

2.2.1 NEEDS BASED ON THE WIDENING UNIVERSITIES ASSESSMENT

In this section, the CBNs identified during the initial assessments of the ULPGC are presented (see Table 4. **CBNs identified in the ULPGC’s assessment and in the assessment of its surrounding ecosystem under WP1.**). These assessments, carried out under Task 1.2 and Task 1.3 of WP1 (as previously discussed in this report), emphasized key areas where specific training and capacity-building activities are deemed crucial to addressing some of the institutional and regional challenges identified.

Table 4. CBNs identified in the ULPGC’s assessment and in the assessment of its surrounding ecosystem under WP1.

WP	Aspect	Barrier	CBN
Attracting and retaining talents (WP3)	Practical skills	Skill gaps in the workforce	To foster <i>educational programs</i> which enhance and focus on <i>applied learning</i> . To replace standalone courses with <i>interconnected, comprehensive skill-building programs</i> . Develop courses with a common theme. Introduce a competency-based learning system to ensure students have mastered the necessary skills before advancing.
	Career development opportunities	Development of complementary competencies	Establish specific programs to <i>incentivize</i> and support <i>workforce diversity</i> , including <i>training</i> , hiring <i>practices</i> or community-building initiatives.
	Workplace balance and wellbeing	Diversity and inclusion initiatives	To provide <i>training for managers</i> on how to support their <i>teams' mental health</i> .
		Concerns about stress and burnout	To develop regular <i>training programs</i> on <i>ethical standards</i> for both research staff and students.
Ethical excellence	Ethics training programs		
Promoting Excellent and Responsible Research (WP4)	Advanced research production	Research and equipment facilities and equipment management	To invest in ongoing <i>training programs</i> for technical staff to enhance their <i>operational skills</i> .
Connection with business environment: knowledge transfer and	KTT Strategies and organizations	KTT Education and training programs	Invest in the creation of comprehensive yet <i>concise workshops, seminars, or webinars</i> . These should focus on imparting a clear understanding of <i>KTT processes</i> , their benefits, and crucial aspects of <i>start-up development</i> .

spinoffs (WP5)	Partnership development	Management professionals	Prioritize investment in hiring or training dedicated personnel who can manage partnerships effectively.
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2.2.2 IDENTIFICATION OF BEST PRACTICES

As previously presented in the case of the UAc, this section outlines the key CBNs identified at ULPGC through the implementation of Task 1.4. Good Practices from Leading Universities, providing a roadmap for strategic improvements and driving actions at the ULPGC.

For this purpose, the CBNs identified at ULPGC are presented below.

Table 5. CBNs identified at ULPGC through the implementation of Task 1.4., following the Best Practice Catalogue from UROS.

WP	Identification of Best Practice (UROS) ²	CBN
Attracting and retaining talents (WP3)	Didactic certificate	Implementation of didactic training to gain new competences in teaching
	Diversity Office	Cultural Awareness Workshops
	Female Mentoring	Skill-Building Workshops for females
	Online Learning Platform	Training and skills updating platform for employees
Promoting Excellent and Responsible Research (WP4)	Communication	Staff Training on IT Communication
	Scientific Qualification Courses	Training on academic writing, reading, project management, etc.
Connection with business environment: knowledge transfer and spinoffs (WP5)	Careers Service	Training in specific skills demanded by companies
	KTT Office	KTT Education and training programs
	Partnerships between Chairs and Industry	To promote Industrial PhD programs
	Patent and Standards Centre	Training on IP protection
	Start-Up and Entrepreneurship Centre	Practical training and Industry relations
Seminars in University Teaching		

² For further information and details on the best practices, please consult the Best Practice Catalogue from UROS at the last section of this report (Section 8. Annex).

2.2.3 STRATEGIC OBJECTIVES & CAPACITY BUILDING ACTIONS PLANNED

The Action Plan for ULPGC is a crucial step towards enhancing the university's research, innovation, and collaboration with the business sector. This plan, outlined in D2.2. Action Plans developed, is based on the findings from the WP1 assessments, which identified both challenges and opportunities at various levels that could influence ULPGC's role as a regional leader in development and competitiveness.

This section summarizes the strategic objectives and specific actions that the ULPGC is already proactively undertaking to address the critical needs identified during the assessments under WP1. These actions are derived from both the Individual Strategy for ULPGC and the Joint Strategy between ULPGC and UAc, focusing on activities related to training and capacity building. The table below outlines these strategic objectives and the associated Capacity Building Actions.

Table 6. Capacity Building Actions Planned set forth in D2.2. Actions Plans Developed (ULPGC)

Strategic Objective (SO)	Capacity Building Action Planned
SO1: Fostering an Entrepreneurial Culture	A1.1. Staff exchanges with project partners to improve the training and skills of ULPGC staff in knowledge transfer, innovation, and spin-offs.
	A1.2. Pilot implementation of the CLAB (Contamination LAB) model at the ULPGC.
	A1.3. Organisation of events and/or courses related to entrepreneurship and business for the Research Community, including expert visits and workshops.
SO2. Promoting Research, Knowledge Transfer, and Innovation	A2.1. Promotion of the training required for RTTP (Registered Technology Transfer Professionals) accreditation of Technical, Administration and Management Staff of the ULPGC.
	A2.2. Organisation of courses, seminars and/or workshops on Knowledge transfer and Innovation for the ULPGC Teaching and Research staff.
	A2.3. Promotion of activities to disseminate research results through the organisation of summer schools, conferences and/or workshops.
SO3. Developing a Committed University	A3.1. Training plan development for ULPGC Teaching and Research staff, addressing transversal skills in research such as Open Science Practices, research data management, responsible research and science education.

These actions, which focus on training and capacity building, are designed to strengthen ULPGC's institutional capabilities, promote a culture of research excellence, and deepen its engagement with the business community and the wider region.

3. CAPACITY BUILDING ACTIVITIES ALREADY IMPLEMENTED IN THE WIDENING UNIVERSITIES

This section presents some of the capacity building and training initiatives that have already been implemented by the Widening Universities. Specifically, it outlines the

activities carried out by the University of the Azores (UAc) and the University of Las Palmas de Gran Canaria (ULPGC). These initiatives are relevant in the context of the EXPER project, as they contribute to addressing some of the CBNs identified throughout the project's evaluation process and already presented in the preceding section of this report. By detailing the existing CBAs, this section provides an overview of the proactive steps these universities have undertaken to enhance their educational, research and innovation capabilities.

3.1. CAPACITY BUILDING ACTIVITIES AT UAC

The University of the Azores (UAc) has undertaken several capacity-building initiatives that were aligned with the Institution internal action plans and Rectory strategy, which although initiated prior to the start of the EXPER project, are closely aligned with many of the Capacity Building Needs (CBNs) identified through the course of the project. Therefore, we have divided this section is two distinct parts:

1. The first part reviews the actions already implemented or currently in progress at UAc, emphasizing how these initiatives address many of the CBNs that were later identified during the project's initial assessment (WP1) and through Task 1.4, "Good Practices from Leading Universities."
2. The second part highlights additional activities conducted by UAc, as detailed in their most recent activity reports and metrics, which further contribute to the university's ongoing capacity-building efforts.

Part 1. Actions implemented/in progress at UAc

The table below illustrates the correspondence between the Capacity Building Needs (CBNs) identified in the EXPER project and a set of concrete actions and work done up to the moment by UAc. The selected actions are thoroughly described, also including in some cases the planned and future activities to achieve this substantial improvement as complementary information. This comparison underscores how UAc's ongoing actions and initiatives effectively address key competencies and development areas, ensuring that its internal staff resources are well-prepared to meet the evolving demands of their roles and daily work.

Table 7. CBNs identified in UAc vs. Actions implemented/in progress by UAc in this specific area.

WP	CBN	Actions implemented/in progress at UAc
Attracting and retaining talents (WP3)	To offer opportunities for professional growth such as training, workshops, or further education. Encourage and support participation in these activities.	Support for teachers and researchers includes various training opportunities. It is worth noting that the UAc is now part of a network of institutions that organize Inter-Institutional Conferences for Pedagogical Development, which are open to higher education teachers interested

		<p>in enhancing their pedagogical skills. These conferences provide valuable opportunities for interaction with national experts and the exchange of experiences with colleagues from other institutions. The conferences offer a diverse range of pedagogical training programs, all of which are conducted online. Over the past two years, five editions of the conferences have been held, providing around 140 training sessions. On average, 25 UAc teachers have participated in each edition. In addition to these conferences, the CFC internally organizes various training sessions. These sessions aim to improve the digital literacy of teachers and researchers and enhance their abilities for teaching, researching, and participating in academic activities conducted remotely. The first training session is already underway in collaboration with the Open University, focusing on certifying UAc teachers and researchers for distance education.</p>
	<p>To develop regular <i>training programs on ethical standards</i> for both research staff and students.</p>	<p>In 2022, UAc elaborated its "Plan for Gender Equality, Inclusion, and Non-Discrimination". This plan focuses on creating a supportive structure, fostering a culture of equality and implementing actions to promote equal opportunities and reduce inequalities and includes the sharing good practices and training actions. It will have a monitoring and implementation timeframe from 2022-2025.</p>
	<p>To cultivate a comprehensive understanding of the university's ethical guidelines and the function of the Ethics Committee: through periodic newsletters, emails, or updates regarding ethical policies and committee activities.</p>	<p>The UAc adopts several measures to defend the integrity of its conducted research, following the guidelines established by the Foundation for Science and Technology (FCT) in its "Code of Ethics in Research". Through the publication of the "Code of Ethics of the University of the Azores", UAc has established clear codes of conduct and ethical principles that guide the behavior of researchers and their practices, guided by three main objectives: (1) ensuring the highest standards of scientific integrity, (2) ensuring the highest ethical standards, and (3) using transparent, fair, and effective processes in evaluating allegations of misconduct that violate the institution's code of ethics. UAc also has an "Ethics Committee", appointed by the Rector, and responsible for analyzing ethical and research integrity issues as well as for issuing opinions and recommendations as deemed necessary. This committee is composed of ethics experts and representatives from the academic community, ensuring an impartial and rigorous review of the issues under analysis.</p>

<p>Promoting Excellent and Responsible Research (WP4)</p>	<p>To develop comprehensive communication strategies to keep faculty, researchers, teachers and students informed about the university's initiatives.</p>	<p>The UAc Portal (uac.pt) ensures the regular publication of information for the academic community, external partners and society. The portal provides up-to-date information on various topics, including the Institution's history, organizational structure, legislation, regulations, plans, reports, quality, evaluation, and codes of conduct and ethics. It also offers information on Teaching and Student Support, such as educational programs, exams, regulations, directives, orders, academic management (academic calendar, schedules, exam calendar, fees, certificates, enrolments and applications), library, archive, social action service (scholarships, accommodation, food, school insurance, health and welfare office, support for students with special educational needs). Additionally, the Portal provides support for international students and information on mobility programs, with a dedicated page in English at international.uac.pt. It covers Research and Innovation, including institutes, research centers and a business incubator. Community Services are also featured, including the Junior Academy, Senior Academy, Career Lab for training and employment, Alumni Network, Sports, Language Exams, Short Courses and Visits to the UAc by basic, secondary, and vocational education students. Moreover, the Portal promotes the "UAc speaks Science" initiative, which aims to disseminate science to the general public, particularly focusing on basic, secondary, and vocational students. The UAc maintains a news page at noticias.uac.pt and has active accounts on popular social media platforms like Facebook, Instagram and LinkedIn. Through these channels, the university continuously promotes events and initiatives of the academic community, training opportunities, contests and more. Furthermore, the Office of Public Relations and Communication regularly sends out emails to both the academic community and the media, disseminating important information. Additionally, a newsletter is sent out every Monday, summarizing the key events of the previous week.</p>
	<p>To establish a dedicated public relations or communications team responsible for showcasing research achievements, both internally and externally.</p>	<p>The Office for Public Relations and Communication regularly sends out emails to both the academic community and the media, disseminating important information. Additionally, a newsletter is sent out every Monday, summarizing the key events of the previous week.</p>
	<p>Acquisition of new skills for researchers and fostering strategies to step them</p>	<p>UAc is aware of the importance of interdisciplinary projects and encourages the interdisciplinarity work between research units and teams. Recently, a</p>

	<p>outside their comfort zones. To facilitate and encourage research centres to host specialists from different scientific fields.</p>	<p>delegation from the University of the Azores (UAc), composed of doctoral students from diverse UAc faculties and led by FCT Assistant Researcher, Andrea Zita Botelho, was present at the Hackathon organized between the 20th and 24th of November 2023 by the University of Sassari (Sardinia Island, Italy). Participants were challenged to reflect on the challenges and opportunities of the ocean and find solutions to them from a multidisciplinary perspective, with the possibility of exchanging ideas and contacting resident researchers.</p>
<p>Connection with business environment: knowledge transfer and spinoffs (WP5)</p>	<p>To strengthen KTT Literacy, implementing, training programs, seminars, and workshops for staff members and researchers. This will help build a comprehensive understanding of KTT processes, importance, and benefits.</p>	<p>In terms of the institutional strategy and policies for knowledge and technology transfer, the creation of InUAc - UAc Technological Incubator in 2020 marked a significant shift in the R&D&I paradigm at the UAc. It has enabled the institution to foster academic entrepreneurship, create an ecosystem to support innovation and knowledge transfer to society, and enhance the UAc's engagement with the business sector. Moreover, the UAc's In its second year of activities, the incubator continued to have a regular presence on digital platforms and social networks and increased its activity by establishing over 20 partnerships, joining 2 incubation networks, involving more than 35 mentors, organizing four events, increasing the number of incubated projects to 11 since 2021, and conducting over 20 mentoring sessions. Overall, InUAc's activities involved over 650 participants and held more than 80 meetings with various stakeholders.</p>
	<p>To Identify the resource needs of KTT. securing additional funding, hiring or training skilled personnel, and efficiently utilizing existing resources. Seek out public, private, and governmental funding opportunities, grants, and partnerships.</p>	<p>It has been recognized since 2022 that InUAc should also be a "Center for Knowledge Transfer and Valorization". Therefore, by incorporating the "Office for Knowledge Transfer and Valorization" into InUAc in Dec/2023, the UAc aims to strengthen itself as a knowledge-producing institution and reinforce its link to the productive sector, fostering the dissemination of knowledge and technologies while promoting synergies. This office will be responsible for intellectual property protection and its market promotion, ensuring economic benefits for all stakeholders, including the UAc. It will serve as a valuable resource for researchers, students and teachers, facilitating the transformation of the knowledge generated at the UAc into innovation and added value. This office should be able to support the socio-economic application of the knowledge generated at the UAc and facilitate intellectual property protection to safeguard competitive advantages and commercial returns on the investment in innovation. To address these challenges, InUAc is</p>

		currently providing training to its three employees in technology-based entrepreneurship, knowledge transfer, intellectual property, and the creation of technology-based businesses. Furthermore, on Jul/2024 UAc has opened a permanent staff position for InUAc Coordinator.
	To offer entrepreneurship training and workshops would help to equip students, faculty, and alumni with the necessary skills for business start-up and development.	InUAc continued to have a regular presence on digital platforms and social networks and increased its activity by establishing over 20 partnerships, joining 2 incubation networks, involving more than 35 mentors, organizing 4 events, increasing the number of incubated projects to 11 since 2021, and conducting over 20 mentoring sessions. Overall, InUAc's activities involved over 650 participants and held more than 80 meetings with various stakeholders. InUAc is also partner of several EU funding projects, such as ATLIC and Innovamos (INTERREG Atlantic Area and MAC, respectively)
	To organize awareness campaigns, workshops, and seminars on entrepreneurship and the benefits of start-up support.	Since its establishing, InUAc has been directly involved in the following main initiatives: - BlueBio Value Ideation Program - Green Up Ideation Program - Tourism Explorers Ideation Program - Bootcamp InUAc - Entrepreneur Fair - InUAc Friday Workshops Many of these events awarded the winners incubation program periods at InUAc. The same practices will be adopted in the next events.

As described, the University of the Azores (UAc) is actively engaging in a series of initiatives that will address a wide range of the identified Capacity Building Needs (CBNs). These needs often encompass areas such as enhancing research capabilities, improving technology transfer implementation, and strengthening institutional frameworks to better support its internal staff. By addressing these needs, UAc is not just reacting to existing gaps but is also strategically positioning itself for future challenges.

This foresight ensures that the university is not just keeping up with current standards but is also preparing its excellence in the emerging areas of Academia. In essence, UAc is creating an environment where continuous professional development and innovation are integral to its mission.

Part 2. UAc activity reports

Institutional strategy and lifelong learning policies:

Since 2003, it has also had the Centre for Complementary Training (CFC) - UAc.forma, whose mission is to promote and enhance short-term training activities aimed at

improving the quality of professional work and requalification, both for its employees, teachers, and students, as well as for the external public.

The training offer of the CFC has sought to meet the interests and training needs of various professional categories, particularly administrative assistants, senior technical staff, and teachers, encompassing different university structures. In this context, there has been an increase in training observed during the pandemic period to support online teaching and remote working (basic skills in Moodle, Zoom, Teams, Educast, MS Forms, Respondus, among others). It is also worth noting that in early 2021, UAc joined the network of institutions that promote the Conferences on Inter-Institutional Pedagogical Development open to higher education teachers interested in their pedagogical professional development. These conferences provide opportunities for interaction between teachers from participating institutions and national experts, as well as the sharing of experiences with colleagues from other institutions through a fully online program of pedagogical training. In recent years, there has also been an offer of open courses, mainly in the field of languages, attended by UAc staff, exchange students, and the general public, particularly in foreign languages and Portuguese as a Foreign Language.

The Centre for Lifelong Learning offers a training programme designed to meet the needs of the institution and the training interests of employees (teaching and non-teaching staff), contributing to their professional development, updating their knowledge, promoting excellence at work, adapting to institutional changes, stimulating innovation, personal growth and well-being and satisfaction at work. In this context, short courses and training sessions have been offered in the areas of languages (also available to the external community), IT tools to support daily routines, entrepreneurship and project management, among others. As an example, to meet the challenges posed by the pandemic, 17 training courses were held to support online teaching and teleworking (basic skills in moodle, zoom, teams, educast, MS forms, respondus, among others). We received 865 registrations from teachers, 76 registrations from employees and 86 registrations from students.

Within this framework, the UAc also offers the external community short courses aimed at updating knowledge and deepening skills, in areas such as: foreign languages, health, economics and management, ecology, pest control, science management, entrepreneurship, some promoted by InUAc and as part of the Living the Future Academy project, in which the UAc is participating as part of a PRR consortium led by the University of Coimbra.

Support structures for teaching and research staff:

Support for teachers and researchers includes various training opportunities. It is worth noting that the UAc is now part of a network of institutions that organize Inter-Institutional Conferences for Pedagogical Development, which are open to higher education teachers interested in enhancing their pedagogical skills. These conferences provide valuable

opportunities for interaction with national experts and the exchange of experiences with colleagues from other institutions. The conferences offer a diverse range of pedagogical training programs, all of which are conducted online. Over the past two years, five editions of the conferences have been held, providing around 140 training sessions. On average, 25 UAc teachers have participated in each edition. In addition to these conferences, the CFC internally organizes various training sessions. These sessions aim to improve the digital literacy of teachers and researchers and enhance their abilities for teaching, researching, and participating in academic activities conducted remotely. The first training session is already underway in collaboration with the Open University, focusing on certifying UAc teachers and researchers for distance education.

InUAc and the SVCT have also organized various training activities, focusing on subjects such as entrepreneurship and marketing. InUAc specifically offers training opportunities for faculty and students to develop innovative technology-based products and services derived from research and facilitate knowledge transfer to the business market. Moreover, the American Corner facilitates English language training.

Support structures for technical and administrative staff:

As far as training is concerned, the UAc makes available to its employees several offers that contribute to improving professional knowledge in the various areas of activity. These training courses are offered by the UAc Centre for Lifelong Learning and, in total, they have involved, on average, a total of 120 employees. In addition, UAc employees were able to benefit from training provided by the Azores Public Administration Training Centre (CeFAPA).

Complementary training data:

The data related to the complementary training of UAc employees (Table 4) indicates a significant fluctuation in the number of registrations and participation in training activities between 2019 and 2023, both internally and externally, with a decrease in participation in internal and external training activities recorded in 2023. A total of 103 training sessions were conducted, and we received a total of 246 registrations from the academic community.

The training offerings have aligned with the training interests of various professional categories, particularly technical assistants, senior technicians, and faculty members (Table 5), and have encompassed different university structures (Table 6).

Table 8. Total registration/participation in training actions for UAc employees.

		2019	2020	2021	2022	2023
Internal	Registrations	9	641	456	75	59
	Participations	9	589	419	75	59
External	Registrations	76	53	4	4	63
	Participations	8	0	4	3	56
Autotraining	Registrations	24	126	186	75	124

	Participations	24	126	186	70	124
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Table 9. Total UAc employees involved in training actions by Career/Category.

Category	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023
Manager	3	8	15	9	6
Senior Technician	6	16	25	13	16
Technical Assistant	6	27	47	15	11
Operational Assistant	-	4	1	0	5
Technical Coordinator	-	4	6	1	2
IT Specialist	3	1	1	1	0
IT Technician	-	6	7	0	1
Teachers	8	137	75	8	38
Investigators	1	4	4	0	7
Fellows	-	2	4	0	2
Interns/Other Employees		1	14	2	30
Total	27	210	199	49	118

Table 10. Total number of UAc employees involved in training actions by Organic Unit / Service

Organic Unit / Service	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023
FCAA	-	21	17	-	7
FCT	4	48	28	4	20
FCSH	3	44	29	2	12
FEG	1	19	7	1	2
ESS	1	19	11	1	1
ESTA	-	1	-	1	-
CHAM-A	-	1	-	-	-
CICS	-	-	2	-	-
IITAA	-	1	1	-	-
IVAR	-	-	3	-	-
OKEANOS	-	-	-	-	29
ADM	-	-	3	1	-
AAUA	-	1	-	-	-
SASE	1	5	10	3	21
BAM	-	5	4	18	6
SISA	-	-	-	-	1
SVCT	6	9	9	-	7
SVRFM	-	1	10	-	-
SVAP	-	-	6	3	-
SVGA	1	10	5	2	-
SVRH	1	2	7	3	-

SRTR	8	17	22	10	11
SVTIC	-	5	7	-	1
FGF	1	1	11	-	-
CEEApIA-A	-	-	1	-	-
CIBIO	-	-	1	-	-
GBA	-	-	5	-	-
Total	27	210	193	49	118

3.2. CAPACITY BUILDING ACTIVITIES AT ULPGC

The University of Las Palmas de Gran Canaria (ULPGC) has implemented a robust strategy for capacity building that, although developed prior to the start of the EXPER project, aligns closely with many of the identified CBNs through it. This section has been divided into two distinct parts. The first part examines the contents of the [Training Plan for Teachers and Research Staff 2021-2025 \(TPTRS 2021-2025\)](#) of the ULPGC, highlighting how this pre-existing plan effectively addresses several of the CBNs later detected in the project's initial evaluation (WP1) and through task 1.4, "Good Practices from Leading Universities". The second part highlights the activities carried out by the Fundación Canaria Parque Científico y Tecnológico de la ULPGC (FCPCT-ULPGC), as reflected in their latest Activity Report, further contributing to the capacity-building efforts at ULPGC.

Part 1. Training Plan for Teachers and Research Staff 2021-2025

The 2021-2025 TPTRS of the ULPGC was designed to strengthen the competencies of faculty and researchers, adapting to both current and future needs. This flexible plan covers key areas such as digital competencies, educational innovation, and the alignment of research and transfer processes, while also supporting the attainment of specific degrees. Based on an analysis of the previous training plan (2017-2021), it adjusts according to demand and continuous evaluation, ensuring quality and sustainability in the training activities.

The following table outlines the alignment between some of the CBNs identified in the EXPER project and the initiatives covered by the 2021-2025 TPTRS at ULPGC. This comparison highlights how the existing capacity building programs at ULPGC address specific competencies and areas of development, ensuring that the university's faculty and researchers are equipped to meet the evolving demands of their roles.

Table 11. CBNs identified in ULPGC vs. Training resources covered by the 2021-2025 TPTRS.

WP	CBN	2021-2025 TPTRS
Attracting and retaining talents (WP3)	Fostering Educational Programs Focused on Applied Learning	The 2021-2025 TPTRS emphasizes innovation in teaching methodologies, with specific training on active learning strategies, project-based learning, and gamification. This directly addresses the need for educational programs that enhance applied

		learning, ensuring that faculty can effectively integrate these methods into their curriculum.
	Replacing Standalone Courses with Comprehensive Skill-Building Programs	The 2021-2025 TPTRS includes the development of interconnected courses and training modules that build on each other, fostering a holistic approach to skill development. By encouraging thematic courses and competency-based learning, ULPGC aligns with the project's goal to replace isolated courses with more cohesive programs.
	Training Platform for Continuous Skills Updating	The university offers a dynamic online platform for continuous professional development, where employees can access training resources, webinars, and online courses. This platform is a crucial tool for ensuring that staff skills remain up-to-date, meeting the need for an ongoing skills updating mechanism.
	Workforce Diversity and Inclusive Practices	The 2021-2025 TPTRS (hereinafter, the Plan) highlights training in cultural awareness and diversity, including workshops that promote inclusive teaching practices. These initiatives support the need for programs that incentivize and support workforce diversity through training and inclusive hiring practices.
	Skill-Building Workshops for Female Staff	The Plan supports gender equity by offering workshops that focus on skill-building for female academics and researchers, addressing the need for tailored programs that support female professionals in academia.
	Training for Managers on Team Mental Health	Although the Plan does not explicitly mention mental health training for managers, the emphasis on leadership development and training in emotional intelligence indirectly supports this need. There is potential for expanding this area within the ongoing professional development programs.
	Regular Training on Ethical Standards	The Plan includes mandatory training on research ethics and academic integrity, ensuring that both research staff and students adhere to the highest ethical standards.
Promoting Excellent and Responsible Research (WP4)	Enhancing Operational Skills of Technical Staff	The Plan incorporates specific training sessions designed to improve the technical and operational skills of staff, such as courses on advanced IT tools, data management, and laboratory techniques.
	Training in Academic Writing, Project Management, and Communication	The Plan includes extensive training in academic writing, research project management, and IT communication skills, directly addressing these specific needs. These sessions are designed to improve the academic and professional capabilities of ULPGC staff.
Connection with business environment: knowledge transfer and	Workshops, Seminars, and Webinars on Knowledge Transfer and Start-up Development	The Plan includes workshops and seminars focused on knowledge transfer, innovation, and entrepreneurship. Additionally, activities related to start-up development are promoted through partnerships with the FCPCT-ULPGC. These initiatives align with the project's goal of imparting a clear understanding of KTT processes.

spinoffs (WP5)	Training on IP protection	The Plan features courses and seminars on IPR and protection, a key component of the training needs identified. This ensures that staff and students are well-versed in protecting their innovations.
	Promotion of Industrial PhD Programs	Although not explicitly detailed in the Plan, the promotion of Industrial PhD programs aligns with the broader university strategy to strengthen ties with industry. The ongoing collaboration with the FCPCT-ULPGC facilitates practical training and enhances industry relations.

Through these initiatives, the ULPGC not only meets many of the identified CBNs but also demonstrates a proactive approach to capacity building that is both comprehensive and forward-looking. The alignment of the Plan with the EXPER project's objectives ensures that the university continues to foster an environment of continuous professional development and innovation.

Part 2. FCPCT Activities report

This second part highlights the activities conducted by the Fundación Canaria Parque Científico y Tecnológico (FCPCT) of the ULPGC, as reflected in their latest activity report (2023) and additional activities undertaken during 2024, further contributing to the capacity-building efforts at ULPGC. The FCPCT plays a crucial role in providing essential infrastructure, technological resources, and value-added services for research, development, and innovation (R&D&I) processes.

As a public foundation closely linked to ULPGC, the FCPCT is responsible for promoting and managing the Science and Technology Park and its affiliated centers. The foundation's objectives include fostering innovation culture, enhancing the competitiveness of resident companies, and facilitating KTT between the university, research institutions, businesses, and markets. Additionally, the FCPCT oversees the economic management of projects in which the ULPGC participates, ensuring that the necessary resources are effectively allocated to support these initiatives. The activity report for 2023, along with the activities conducted in 2024, provides a comprehensive overview of these efforts, showcasing the foundation's significant contribution to the university's capacity-building initiatives.

A summary of the main activities developed by the offices of the FCPCT-ULPGC during 2023 and 2024 is presented below, which have significantly contributed to strengthening the research, development, and innovation capacities at the University of Las Palmas de Gran Canaria.

European Projects Office (OPE):

The OPE has been actively involved in enhancing the skills of the ULPGC research community, particularly in securing European funding and participating in international research networks. Key activities include:

- **Training modules:** Offering training on internationalization and securing European funds, as part of the Continuous Training Plan for Teaching and Research Staff (PDI) and the Doctoral School of ULPGC.
- **Networking and collaboration:** Participating in technical conferences and meetings with other entities in the Canary Islands' R&D&I system, fostering collaboration and knowledge exchange.
- **Technical staff training:** Ongoing training for OPE staff, especially in the new Horizon Europe Program, covering topics such as financial aspects, data management, and protection of results.
- **Workshops and seminars:** Organizing workshops on European project coordination, financial management, and proposal writing to strengthen the skills of both researchers and administrative staff.

Knowledge Transfer Office (OTC):

The OTC has undertaken various activities to promote innovation and knowledge transfer. Among its main initiatives, the following stand out:

- **Promotion of collaboration:** Encouraging strategic alliances between the university, research institutions, businesses, and markets to drive innovation and technological development.
- **Organization of meetings:** Coordinating meetings and forums with the business sector to identify opportunities for KTT.
- **Participation in events:** Representing ULPGC at national and international events, enhancing the visibility of technological offerings and establishing new contacts.
- **Management of training programs:** Implementing specialized courses and workshops in key areas for knowledge transfer and innovation, aimed at the academic and business communities.
- **Value-added services:** Providing services that support the economic and administrative management of R&D&I projects, facilitating participation in initiatives for the transfer of research results.

Industrial and Intellectual Property Office (OPII):

The OPII has significantly advanced ULPGC's efforts in protecting and commercializing its research outputs. Key activities include:

- **Patent applications:** Since its establishment in 2015, OPII has filed more inventions in eight years than in the university's first 25 years, with significant financial returns from technology and software transfer contracts.
- **International presence:** Doubling the number of European and international patent applications in the past two years compared to the entire previous history of ULPGC.
- **Patents Week:** Reviving and expanding the Patents Week event post-pandemic, making it a national reference in technology transfer.
- **Training and awareness:** Conducting IP rights training and awareness programs, attracting more researchers and students to seek advice on intellectual property and technology transfer.
- **International networking:** Active participation in international innovation ecosystems, including programs like Start-Up Nation Israel and visits to leading universities in spin-off creation.
- **Contract support:** Advising ULPGC personnel on industrial and intellectual property aspects when signing contracts with companies, ensuring the university retains its rights and benefits from research outputs.

To conclude this section, we will briefly highlight the most important capacity-building activities conducted and organised by ULPGC under the EXPER Project during RP2, focusing specifically on the activities related to WPs 3, 4, 5 and 6. Further details on the content and scope of these training initiatives for the university community and relevant stakeholders will be expanded upon later in this report (Section 6: Report on Capacity Building Activities). The following table presents this information.

Table 12. CBAs conducted by FCPCT-ULPGC to the date of writing the present report (RP2).

WP	Event name	Date	Description
Attracting and retaining talents (WP3)	CLAB activities	In progress	Implementation of the CLAB Model at ULPGC.
Connection with	Conference	21-02-2024	Colloquium on Innovation and internationalisation with ICEX Director

business environment: knowledge transfer and spinoffs (WP5)	Staff Exchange (KIT)	12-13 June 2024	ULPGC delegation visits KIT in Germany for KTT insights
	From Research to Idea	June and July 2024	Training sessions focused on capacity building on technology transfer and market-driven activities.
3 to 5	Summer School	17-19 July 2024	Training event in research management, focusing on Open Science and strategic use of Horizon Europe, ERC, and EIC funding opportunities.
Sustainability and Exploitation (WP6)	University-Business Collaboration	13-06-2024	Training session: Support Tools to Incentivize and Promote University-Business Collaboration through R&D&I Taxation

4. CAPACITY BUILDING PLANS

4.1. CBP OF THE UAC

The Capacity Building Plan (CBP) of the University of the Azores (UAc) is a strategic initiative aimed at significantly enhancing the university's capabilities in research, innovation, and knowledge transfer. At its core, the CBP seeks to elevate the skills and competencies of UAc's academic and administrative staff, thereby strengthening the institution's overall capacity to contribute to research and drive meaningful innovation. However, the scope of the CBP extends beyond just the university's internal stakeholders; it also seeks to engage and empower the broader community of stakeholders, including industry partners, policymakers, and the general public, ensuring that the benefits of the university's advancements in research and innovation are widely shared.

By developing the competencies of its staff and stakeholders, UAc aims to better respond to the demands of modern research environments and to play a pivotal role in regional and international development. This involves not only improving traditional academic skills but also embracing a range of transversal skills — those that are transferable across different fields and contexts, such as project management, science communication, open science, proposal writing, responsible research and scientific education.

The alignment of the CBP with Task 4.3 of the EXPER project, which focuses on developing transversal skills for excellent and responsible research, underscores the strategic foresight embedded in UAc's approach. This task emphasizes the importance of transversal and research management skills, which are increasingly recognized as vital for researchers and academic institutions to thrive in the competitive and complex landscape of European research funding and collaboration.

4.1.1 OBJECTIVES

The table below provides a comprehensive overview of the primary objectives outlined for the UAc's CBP, which aims to significantly enhance the university's capabilities in research, innovation, and knowledge transfer. Each objective is designed to address critical areas of development and to align with the broader goals of advancing academic excellence and societal impact.

Table 13. Objectives of the UAc's CBP

Objective	Description
<p>1. Promote transversal skills for excellence in research</p>	<p>Promote advanced competencies in research management, like proposal writing and project execution, particularly within the context of European and international research funding programs. Provide training in Open Science practices and digital competencies among UAc staff, in order to raise awareness of emerging research publication practices. This includes integrating training activities foreseen in WP4 to enhance research management skills.</p>
<p>2. Strengthen KTT and Innovation</p>	<p>Foster a better KTT between the Academia and applicable stakeholders (industry and society) by providing research staff with the tools and know-how on innovation market-driven practices, business modelling, IPR management and spin-off supporting.</p>
<p>3. Foster scientific education and societal involvement</p>	<p>Offer the necessary skills for responsible research practices, scientific education and science communication, to effective dissemination of research results to society and foster the participation in scientific outreach events that connect researchers with society. This includes integrating training and foreseen activities under WP4.</p>
<p>4. Stakeholders engagement and Internationalization</p>	<p>Offer training to external partners (industry, science and technology parks, competent authorities, chambers of commerce, general public), which can increase their skills to facilitate collaborative projects with UAc, thus contributing to regional development. Maximize UAc's potential to integrate R&D+i networks, either by increasing its EU funding project participation (through European University Alliances) and by fostering the continuous participation in mobility programs</p>

4.1.2 STRATEGY

To achieve the objectives of the CBP, as detailed in the previous section, UAc is set to execute a strategy designed to align with its overarching goals of advancing research excellence and fostering innovation. This strategic approach is critical for transforming

the university landscape and ensuring its contributions to the broader academic and societal ecosystem.

The UAc's strategy is based on the following guiding institutional principles: (i) adapting educational offerings to the needs of the RAA and regional, national, and international demands; (ii) enhancing scientific production and the potential for knowledge transfer; (iii) reinforcing quality, efficiency, and effectiveness; (iv) expanding cooperation and gaining national and international recognition, as well as fostering community engagement; (v) promoting the well-being of the academic community and enhancing academic spirit and experiences; and (vi) ensuring the institution's financial sustainability, and encompasses the following:

1. Staff training and support

In addition to the Centre for Complementary Training (CFC) - UAc.forma activities, UAc will carry on additional EXPER trainings which include foreseen activities under the WP4, and provide support, especially researchers, in specific needs and transversal skills such as expertise in Open Science, Science Communication, Project writing and Technology Transfer practices, aiming to build competencies that are directly relevant to contemporary research and funding environments. Additionally, through EXPER actions and InUAc activities, direct support to researchers and spin-offs will be provided. These trainings will be conducted with the support of various institutions and external experts, including the University of Coimbra, the Pedro Nunes Institute (IPN), the National Institute of Industrial Property (INPI) and EXPER partners such as ATRINEO AG.

2. Stakeholder engagement and Internationalization

External stakeholders, such as industry, science and technology parks, competent authorities, chambers of commerce and general public, will be also involved in the foreseen training actions to foster their skills increase and future collaborations, in line with the strategic objectives of the UAc's EXPER Individual Strategy.

UAc internationalization strategy will be focused explicitly on i) staff mobility, ii) science and knowledge transfer, and iii) education.

- i. Increase academic mobility enhancing the institution's external visibility, strengthening its network of contacts and partnerships with foreign HEIs, and promoting the competencies of its internal staff;
- ii. Foster new collaborations and participate in new European and international R&D projects; lay the foundations for a "European University Alliance", which will promote integrated cooperation between the research and innovation dimension and the education and training dimension; foster the participation in entrepreneurship networks.
- iii. Maintain and increase the existing international educational programs, such as the current PhD programs in association with the University of Las Palmas de Gran Canaria, the University of La Laguna, the University of Corsica

Pasquale Paoli, and the Institut National des Langues et Civilisations Occidentales.

4.1.3 ACTIONS AND WORK PLAN

This section outlines the actions and a detailed work plan necessary to achieve the outlined objectives. The CBAs are complementary to those specified in D2.2: Action Plans Developed (refer to Table 3. Capacity Building Actions Planned set forth in D2.2. Actions Plans Developed (UAc) of this report), ensuring no overlap and facilitating effective progress monitoring. The CBAs from D2.2 remain integral to UAc's capacity-building goals under the EXPER project and will continue to be monitored.

The table below connects the CBP objectives with the related actions and their descriptions. Additionally, a Gantt Chart is provided to display the actions implementation timeline throughout the project period, ending in March 2025, and beyond, highlighting the long-term execution of certain actions within UAc.

Table 14. Objectives of the UAc's CBP and associated actions

CBP Objective	Associated Actions	Description
1. Promote transversal skills for excellence in research	Action 1.1: Research Project Management Training	Implement trainings focused on research project management, as proposal writing with a particular focus on Horizon Europe funding programme.
	Action 1.2: Workshops on Best Practices in Science Communication	Organize training workshops to share Best Practices in Science Communication field, in order to foster the use of research results into educations.
	Action 1.3: Development of competencies in Open Science	Offer training on Open Science good practices, aligned with Horizon Europe standards, as part of Task 4.3.
	Action 1.4: Implementation of Digital Tools	Integrate and improve digital tools that facilitate an updated informational platform for the external funded projects.
2. Strengthen KTT and Innovation	Action 2.1: Enhancement of the Innovation and KTT	Promote training of teaching and research staff in various skills to enhance their performance in technology transfer activities and foster the support activities of the Technology Transfer Office (TTO) within the InUAc department.
3. Foster scientific education and societal involvement	Action 3.1: Scientific Outreach Activities	Participate in scientific outreach events that connect researchers with society, promoting the use of research results in education and other sectors.

4. Stakeholders engagement and Internationalization	Action 4.1: Training external partners in collaboration with the UAc	To provide training to external partners, including companies and R&I promotion agents, to facilitate their engagement in collaborative projects with UAc, thus contributing to regional development.
	Action 4.2: Enhancement of the Regional and International networks	To enhance the regional innovation networks and fostering stronger collaborations. This includes for instance, the RIEA (Azores Business Incubator Network) and MetaRedX (Collaborative Network of Entrepreneurship Units and Workshops in Ibero-American Higher Education Institutions) which aims to promote entrepreneurship in HEIs through active collaboration among eight countries, fostering a collaborative workspace and sharing best practices.
	Action 4.3: Integrate and maintain the participation on EUAs	Establish actions to promote cooperation and institutional internationalization, such as the participation on European University Alliances.
	Action 4.4: International Mobility Programs	Encourage participation in international mobility programs to strengthen research networks and global collaboration.

Figure 1. Timeline for the implementation of the CBAs included in the CBP of the UAc

■ Completed during the project ■ Continuation beyond the project

4.1.4 KPIS

To ensure effective oversight of the actions detailed in the CBP, we have developed a set of Key Performance Indicators (KPIs). These KPIs are designed to serve as quantifiable measures to track the advancement and effectiveness of each corresponding action, helping to ensure that goals are achieved within the specified deadlines. By monitoring these indicators, we can pinpoint areas of success and areas needing improvement, enabling timely modifications and supporting ongoing success beyond the project's duration.

Table 15. Strategic objectives of the UAc's CBP and corresponding KPIs

CBP Objective	KPIs	Responsible department/s
1. Promote transversal skills for excellence in research	K1.1 Number of participants attending the trainings on European project writing and Science Communication	SVCT
	K1.2 Number of submitted proposals to European calls	SVCT
	K1.3 Number of Trainings Organized	SVCT
	K1.4 Number of participants attending the trainings on Open Science good practices	SVCT
	K1.5 Number of projects in the Information Platform for external funded projects	SVCT
2. Strengthen KTT and Innovation	K2.1 Number of UAc staff with training in key skills for technology transfer	InUAc
	K2.2 Number of KTT promoted training events	InUAc
3. Foster scientific education and societal involvement	K3.1 Number of events with UAc organization / participation	ProCIED
4. Stakeholders engagement and Internationalization	K4.1 Number of external partners trained	SCVT / InUAc
	K4.2 Number of active UAc networks	VReEGA / VReBECEI / VReAPI / VReCITC / SVCT / InUAc

	K4.3 Number of active collaborative protocols	VReEGA / VReEBECI / VReAPI / VReCITC / SVCT / InUAc
	K4.4 Number of European University Alliances participation	VReCITC
	K4.5 Number of UAc staff participating in mobility programs	ProCIED

4.1.5 MITIGATION AND CONTINGENCY RISKS

As the UAc moves forward with the implementation of its CBP, several potential risks could obstruct the successful attainment of the set objectives. This section outlines the potential risks linked to each objective and action, including their probability of occurrence, severity level, and proposed mitigation measures.

The following table provides a summary of these identified risks, along with their probabilities, severity levels, and the preventive and corrective measures planned to address them:

Table 16. Critical risks & risk management strategy of the UAc's CBP

CBP Objective	Associated Actions	Potential Risk	Proposed preventive and corrective measures
1. Promote transversal skills for excellence in research	Action 1.1: Research Project Management Training	Low participation due to lack of interest or awareness. Probability: Medium; Severity: Medium	Preventive measure: To Implement targeted awareness campaigns and highlight the benefits of the training program. Corrective measure: To offer flexible scheduling or online options to increase accessibility and participation.
	Action 1.2: Workshops on Best Practices in Science Communication	Insufficient engagement from researchers. Probability: Low; Severity: Medium	Preventive measure: Engage department heads to promote workshops and encourage participation. Corrective measure: Collect feedback to adjust future workshops to meet researchers' needs
	Action 1.3: Development of competencies in Open Science	Resistance to adopting new practices among researchers.	Preventive measure: Provide clear guidance on the benefits and necessary steps for the adoption of these new practices.
	Action 1.4: Implementation of Digital Tools	Low adoption of Digital Tools. Probability: Medium; Severity: High	Preventive measure: Regularly review tool usage and maintain and update the project's information in the Platform for external funded projects. Corrective measure: Allocate more internal staff to the platform update actions.
2. Strengthen KTT and Innovation	Action 2.1: Enhancement of the Innovation and KTT	Low number of internal staff with technological transfer competencies. Probability: Medium; Severity: Medium	Preventive measure: To Implement targeted awareness campaigns and highlight the benefits of such training programs. Corrective measure: To offer flexible scheduling or online options to increase accessibility and participation.

<p>3. Foster scientific education and societal involvement</p>	<p>Action 3.1: Scientific Outreach Activities</p>	<p>Low attendance to the events. Probability: Medium; Severity: High</p>	<p>Preventive measure: Increase promotional activities and partnerships with educational entities and local media. Corrective measure: Re-schedule events, diversify event types and explore online formats.</p>
<p>4. Stakeholders engagement and Internationalization</p>	<p>Action 4.1: Training external partners in collaboration with the UAc</p>	<p>Limited external partner engagement. Probability: Medium; Severity: High</p>	<p>Preventive measure: Build strong communication channels and demonstrate the value of participation. Corrective measure: Tailor training programs to address specific needs and interests of external partners.</p>
	<p>Action 4.2: Enhancement of the Regional and International networks</p>	<p>Low activity levels within the networks. Probability: Medium; Severity: High</p>	<p>Preventive measure: Regularly communicate with network members and organize engaging activities. Corrective measure: Revitalize the networks by introducing new services, events, and collaboration opportunities.</p>
	<p>Action 4.3: Integrate and maintain the participation on EUAs</p>	<p>Difficulty in integrating new EUAs. Probability: Medium; Severity: High</p>	<p>Preventive measure: Maximize international contacts and collaborative efforts in order to join a new EUA consortium and submit new proposals. Corrective measure: Actively participate in the existing EUA in order to enrich and enlarge the international collaboration with HEIs.</p>
	<p>Action 4.4: International Mobility Programs</p>	<p>Low participation in mobility programs due to logistical issues. Probability: Low; Severity: Medium</p>	<p>Preventive measure: Simplify the application process and provide clear information on benefits and logistics. Corrective measure: Work with international partners to resolve logistical challenges and offer virtual mobility options.</p>

Overall, this section outlines a strategy for predicting and mitigating potential challenges, keeping the CBP aligned with its objectives. By taking a proactive approach to risk management, UAc can increase the chances of successfully implementing the CBP, leading to a sustainable and meaningful impact.

4.2. CBP OF THE ULPGC

The CBP of the ULPGC is designed to enhance the research, innovation, and knowledge transfer capabilities of the university by developing the skills and competencies of its academic and administrative staff, as well as its broader stakeholder community. This plan aligns with Task 4.3. Transversal skills for excellent and responsible research of the EXPER project, which focuses on developing transversal and research management skills such as Open Science, research data management in Horizon Europe projects, responsible research, or scientific education to foster the use of Horizon Europe research results into education.

4.2.1 OBJECTIVES

The following table outlines the primary objectives of the ULPGC's CBP, which are designed to enhance the university's research, innovation, and knowledge transfer capabilities. These objectives focus on strengthening research excellence, promoting innovation, fostering international collaboration, advancing digital and open science skills, encouraging responsible research practices, and empowering external stakeholders.

Table 17. Objectives of the ULPGC's CBP

Objective	Description
1. Strengthening Research Excellence	To elevate the university's research outputs by fostering advanced competencies in research management, proposal writing and project execution, particularly within the context of European and international research funding programs. This includes integrating training activities under WP3 and WP4 to enhance research management skills.
2. Fostering Responsible Research and Societal Impact	Equip researchers with the skills necessary for responsible research practices, scientific education, and the effective dissemination of research results to society. This objective directly supports Task 4.3's aim to better connect researchers' work with societal needs, encouraging the use of Horizon Europe research results in educational settings.
3. Developing Digital and Open Science Skills	Advance the adoption of Open Science practices and digital competencies across the university, ensuring that researchers and staff can effectively manage and share research data, engage with global scientific communities, and adhere to

	emerging research standards. Specifically, this includes addressing Task 4.3's focus on open science practices and research data management in Horizon Europe projects.
4. Promoting Innovation and KTT	Facilitate the KTT between the university, industry, and society by equipping staff and researchers with the tools and know-how to protect IP, engage in public-private partnerships, and drive entrepreneurial initiatives.
5. Empowering Stakeholders	Equip external partners, including companies and research promotion agents, with the necessary skills to engage in collaborative projects with the ULPGC, contributing to regional development and the broader innovation ecosystem.
5. Enhancing International collaborations	Improve the ULPGC's global research and innovation networks by training participants to effectively navigate and leverage European frameworks like Horizon Europe Programme, fostering stronger international collaborations and securing additional funding.

4.2.2 STRATEGY

To achieve the objectives of the CBP, already showcased in the previous section, ULPGC will implement a comprehensive strategy that aligns with the university's broader goals of enhancing research excellence and innovation. The strategy will be centered on the following crucial approaches:

A) Integrative Training Programs

Develop and implement training programs that combine theoretical knowledge with practical application. These programs will focus on enhancing research management skills, with a particular emphasis on Open Science practices, research data management in Horizon Europe projects and responsible research practices.

B) Targeted Support and Mentorship

Provide tailored support and mentorship to researchers, particularly early-career researchers, to help them develop the skills and knowledge needed to excel in their fields. This support will be aligned with the specific needs identified in Task 4.3, including fostering skills in Open Science, responsible research, and scientific education.

C) Continuous Monitoring and Adaptation

Establish mechanisms for the ongoing monitoring and evaluation of the training programs to ensure they remain relevant and effective. This will include gathering feedback from participants and stakeholders and adapting the programs as needed to address emerging challenges and opportunities.

D) Collaborative Networks

Foster partnerships with other universities, research institutions, and external experts to share best practices and resources. These collaborations will help to enhance the quality and impact of training programs and ensure that they are aligned with the latest developments in the field.

E) Stakeholder engagement

Engage with external stakeholders, including industry partners and policymakers, to ensure that the training programs are aligned with the needs of the broader research and innovation ecosystem. This engagement will also help to promote the application of research results in society, in line with the strategic objectives of the ULPGC Individual Strategy developed within the framework of the EXPER Project.

4.2.3 ACTIONS AND WORK PLAN

Whereas the objectives of the CBP have already been clearly stated, this section aims to define the specific actions that will be implemented to achieve these objectives and a realistic work plan. The CBAs presented in this section have been designed to be distinct and complementary to those already included in D 2.2: Action Plans Developed (see Table 6. Capacity Building Actions Planned set forth in D2.2. Actions Plans Developed (ULPGC)), ensuring that there is no duplication of effort, and that progress is effectively monitored. These existing CBAs, previously embedded in D. 2.2, also form an integral part of the ULPGC's capacity-building objectives within the framework of the EXPER project and will likewise be closely monitored.

On the other hand, many of the actions outlined in the ULPGC's CBP have already been successfully implemented within the institution, yielding excellent results. This track record of effectiveness is a key reason why we seek to continue and expand upon these initiatives through the EXPER project. By extending these training actions and ensuring their sustainability over time, we aim to build on the progress already made and further enhance the capacity of our institution.

The following table relates the objectives of the CBP with the associated actions and their corresponding descriptions. Following the table, a Gantt Chart will be presented to illustrate the timeline for the implementation of these CBAs, both during the project period (which concludes in March 2025) and beyond, emphasizing the sustainability of certain CBAs within the ULPGC.

Table 18. Objectives of the ULPGC's CBP and associated actions

CBP Objective	Associated Actions	Description
1. Strengthening Research Excellence	Action 1.1: Targeted Training Courses on Research Project Management	Offer targeted training courses focused on key aspects of research project management, including proposal writing, resource planning, and project implementation, with a special emphasis on European and international funding programs.
	Action 1.2: Workshops on Best Practices in Research Management	Organize workshops to share Best Practices in Research Management within the ULPGC.
2. Fostering Responsible Research and Societal Impact	Action 2.1: Scientific Outreach Activities	Organize scientific outreach events that connect researchers with society, promoting the use of research results in education and other sectors.
3. Developing digital and Open Science skills	Action 3.1: Development of competencies in Open Science and Data Management	Offer specialized training actions on Open Science practices and Research Data Management, aligned with Horizon Europe standards, as part of Task 4.3.
	Action 3.2: Implementation of Infrastructures for Open Science	Integrate and improve infrastructures and digital tools that facilitate open access publishing and research data management and sharing, ensuring alignment with current regulatory requirements.
4. Promoting Innovation and KTT	Action 4.1: Awareness Campaign for the OTC Platform of the ULPGC	Launch a comprehensive awareness campaign aimed at increasing the knowledge and understanding of the university community and other stakeholders about the existence, utility, and services offered by the OTC Platform of the ULPGC.
5. Empowering Stakeholders	Action 5.1: Training external partners in collaboration with the ULPGC	To provide training to external partners, including companies and R&I promotion agents, to facilitate their engagement in collaborative projects with ULPGC, thereby contributing to regional development.

	Action 5.2: Training Activities and Workshops for CIDE Network Technicians	This action aims to enhance the expertise of CIDE Network technicians by providing specialized training on R&D transfer from research institutions. While these technicians are already well-versed in business innovation management, this initiative seeks to equip them with knowledge on how to effectively facilitate collaboration between companies and research organizations.
6. Enhancing International collaborations	Action 6.1: Training on European Research and Innovation Frameworks	Conduct training sessions to improve researchers' competencies in navigating and leveraging European frameworks like Horizon Europe, fostering stronger international collaborations.
	Action 6.2: Attracting International Talent through European Projects	This action aims to provide targeted guidance and support to our research staff regarding MSCA (Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions) and ERC (European Research Council) calls, with the goal of attracting top international talent to ULPGC.

Complementary CBAs previously defined at ULPGC (D2.2. Actions Plans developed): See Table 6. Capacity Building Actions Planned set forth in D2.2. Actions Plans Developed (ULPGC) of this report.

Figure 2. Timeline for the implementation of the CBAs included in the CBP of the ULPGC

4.2.4 KPIS

To effectively monitor the implementation and success of the actions previously outlined in the CBP, a set of Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) has been established. These KPIs serve as measurable benchmarks to assess the progress and impact of each action, ensuring that the objectives are met within the designated timeframe. By systematically tracking these indicators, we can identify areas of strength and opportunities for improvement, allowing for timely adjustments and sustained success beyond the project's lifecycle. The following KPIs are tailored to each action, providing clear metrics to guide and evaluate the ULPGC efforts:

Table 19. Strategic objectives of the ULPGC's CBP and corresponding KPIs

CBP Objective	KPIs	Responsible department/s
1. Strengthening Research Excellence	K1.1 Percentage of participants reporting improved competence in Research Project Management.	OPE
	K1.2 Percentage of successfully submitted proposals to European calls	OPE
	K1.3 Number of Workshops Organized	VRRT, OPE
2. Fostering Responsible Research and Societal Impact	K2.1 Number of events organized	VRRT, OPE
	K2.2 Number of participating educational entities (schools, high schools, etc.)	VRRT, OPE
3. Developing digital and Open Science skills	K3.1 Number of training actions delivered	VRRT, VRTAE, OPE
	K3.2 Number of attendants to the training actions delivered	VRRT, VRTAE, OPE
	K3.3 Percentage increase in the adoption of Open Science Practices and Data management.	VRRT, UAI
4. Promoting Innovation and KTT	K4.1 Social media outreach of the information campaign.	OTC

5. Empowering Stakeholders	K5.1 Number of external partners trained	OPE, OTC
	K5.2 Number of training courses or workshops conducted for CIDE network technicians on R&D transfer from research organizations	OTC
6. Enhancing International collaborations	K6.1 Number of projects funded by HE programme.	OPE
	K6.2 Number of MSCA and ERC proposals evaluated and advised by the OPE.	VRRT, OPE

4.2.5 MITIGATION AND CONTINGENCY RISKS

In the implementation of the CBP of the ULPGC, various potential risks may hinder the successful achievement of the defined objectives. Identifying these risks, assessing their likelihood and severity, and preparing effective mitigation strategies are crucial steps to ensure the CBP's success. This section presents an overview of the potential risks associated with each objective and action, along with their probability of occurrence, severity level, and proposed mitigation measures.

Below is a table summarizing the identified risks, their associated probabilities, severities, and the preventive and corrective measures to address them:

Table 20. Critical risks & risk management strategy of the ULPGC's CBP

CBP Objective	Associated Actions	Potential Risk	Proposed preventive and corrective measures
1. Strengthening Research Excellence	Action 1.1: Targeted Training Courses on Research Project Management	Low participation or engagement from research staff due to scheduling conflicts or lack of perceived relevance. <i>Probability:</i> Medium; <i>Severity:</i> Medium	Preventive measure: Conduct a needs assessment survey prior to course development to tailor the training content to the specific needs and schedules of the research staff, ensuring the topics are relevant and beneficial. Corrective measure: If participation is low, offer additional sessions at different times or formats (e.g., recorded webinars, modular courses) to accommodate diverse schedules and increase accessibility.
	Action 1.2: Workshops on Best Practices in Research Management	Insufficient engagement from researchers. <i>Probability:</i> Low; <i>Severity:</i> Medium	Preventive measure: Engage department heads to promote workshops and encourage participation. Corrective measure: Collect feedback to adjust future workshops to meet researchers' needs
2. Fostering Responsible Research and Societal Impact	Action 2.1: Scientific Outreach Activities	Low attendance to the events. <i>Probability:</i> Medium; <i>Severity:</i> High	Preventive measure: Increase promotional activities and partnerships with educational entities and local media. Corrective measure: Re-schedule events, diversify event types and explore online formats.
3. Developing digital and Open Science skills	Action 3.1: Development of competencies in Open Science and Data Management	Resistance to adopting new practices among researchers. <i>Probability:</i> Medium; <i>Severity:</i> High	Preventive measure: Provide clear guidance on the benefits and necessary steps for the adoption of these new practices. Corrective measure: Offer additional support and resources, such as personalized coaching and incentives.
	Action 3.2: Implementation of Infrastructures for Open Science	Low adoption of new Open Science infrastructures if the institutional policies for curricular evaluation are not adequately reoriented to	Preventive measure: Collaborate with university leadership, academic committees, and policy-makers to review and, if necessary, adjust the curricular evaluation criteria to recognize and reward Open Science practices, such as open-access publishing, data sharing, and

		<p>support and incentivize Open Science practices among researchers and faculty members.</p> <p>Probability: Medium; Severity: High</p>	<p>collaborative research. Conduct awareness campaigns and workshops that highlight how adopting Open Science can be beneficial for researchers' career advancement within the institution's revised evaluation framework.</p> <p>Corrective measure: Monitor the alignment between Open Science infrastructures and institutional evaluation policies regularly. To initiate a policy review process with relevant stakeholders to propose amendments that better reflect the university's commitment to Open Science. Provide targeted training and incentives to encourage researchers to adopt Open Science practices, ensuring they are fully integrated and recognized in the academic evaluation process.</p>
4. Promoting Innovation and KTT	Action 4.1: Awareness Campaign for the OTC Platform of the ULPGC	<p>Low engagement or interest from the target audience (researchers, businesses, and other stakeholders), leading to limited participation in the campaign and underutilization of the OTC platform.</p> <p>Probability: Medium; Severity: Medium</p>	<p>Preventive measure: Develop a targeted communication strategy that tailors messages to different stakeholder groups, highlighting specific benefits relevant to each group (e.g., businesses, researchers, and students). Use multiple channels (social media, newsletters, workshops, etc.) to maximize reach and engagement. Involve key influencers and stakeholders early to advocate for the campaign.</p> <p>Corrective measure: If initial engagement is lower than expected, adjust the campaign strategy by incorporating more interactive and engaging content such as webinars, success stories, and live Q&A sessions. Additionally, conduct follow-up surveys to understand the reasons for low participation and refine the campaign based on this feedback to better align with stakeholders' needs and expectations.</p>
5. Empowering Stakeholders	Action 5.1: Training external partners in collaboration with the ULPGC	Limited external partner engagement.	Preventive measure: Build strong communication channels and demonstrate the value of participation.

		Probability: Medium; Severity: High	Corrective measure: Tailor training programs to address specific needs and interests of external partners.
	Action 5.2: Training Activities and Workshops for CIDE Network Technicians	Resistance or reluctance from CIDE Network technicians to engage with the new R&D transfer content, possibly due to perceived complexity or lack of prior experience in this area. Probability: Medium; Severity: Medium	Preventive measure: Collaborate with CIDE network leaders to create a training program tailored to technicians' needs and reinforce the practical benefits of R&D transfer skills in complementing their current expertise. Corrective measure: If initial engagement is low, provide tailored mentorship from both external and local experienced R&D professionals. Additionally, offer follow-up workshops that provide hands-on, practical experience in facilitating collaborations between companies and research institutions
6. Enhancing International collaborations	Action 6.1: Training on European Research and Innovation Frameworks	Challenges in securing funding from European Union programs. Probability: Medium; Severity: High	Preventive measure: Provide detailed guidance on application processes and identify potential collaborators early. Corrective measure: Offer additional workshops on proposal writing and preparation and seek alternative funding sources.
	Action 6.2: Attracting International Talent through European Projects	Insufficient interest or success in securing MSCA and ERC grants, leading to a shortfall in attracting top international talent. Probability: Medium; Severity: High	Preventive measure: Provide comprehensive, targeted workshops and one-on-one advisory sessions to guide researchers through the application process for MSCA and ERC grants, ensuring they are well-prepared and supported. Corrective measure: If the number of successful applications remains low, implement a feedback loop where unsuccessful applicants can receive detailed feedback and tailored support for future submissions, potentially including mock reviews or peer consultations to improve application quality.

In summary, this section provides a framework for anticipating and addressing potential setbacks, ensuring that the CBP remains on track and achieves its intended goals. By proactively managing these risks, ULPGC can enhance the likelihood of success for the CBP, ensuring a sustainable and impactful outcome.

5. IMPACT AND COMMUNICATION ACTIVITIES

The CBP is a strategic initiative jointly implemented by the University of Las Palmas de Gran Canaria (ULPGC) and the University of Azores (UAc). Within the framework of the EXPER Project, this plan is designed to create significant impacts on various target audiences within both universities and their broader ecosystems. By engaging key stakeholders, including university students, researchers, professors, project managers, knowledge transfer officers, and entrepreneurs, the CBP aims to foster a more robust and dynamic research and innovation environment across both institutions.

Both ULPGC and UAc play vital roles in shaping their respective regions, contributing to societal advancement through research, innovation, education, culture, and sustainability. The impact of these universities extends beyond academia, influencing social cohesion, economic growth, and regional development. Therefore, it is crucial that the actions and outcomes of the CBP are effectively communicated to ensure that the benefits are widely recognized and leveraged by all relevant stakeholders.

This section outlines the communication strategies that will be employed by both ULPGC and UAc to disseminate the CBP's activities and achievements. These strategies will target both internal and external audiences, ensuring comprehensive engagement and awareness of the plan's impact across the regions these HEIs serve.

5.1. UAC

The UAc strategy for CBP dissemination and communication encompass the UAc Portal (uac.pt), which ensures the regular publication of information for the academic community, external partners and society all in line with the outlined in D7.1 of the EXPER project. The portal provides up-to-date information on various topics, including the Institution's history, organizational structure, legislation, regulations, plans, reports, quality, evaluation, and codes of conduct and ethics.

Additionally, the Portal provides support for international students and information on mobility programs. It covers Research and Innovation, including institutes, research centers and a business incubator. Moreover, the Portal promotes the "UAc speaks Science" initiative, which aims to disseminate science to the general public, particularly focusing on basic, secondary, and vocational students.

The UAc maintains a news page at noticias.uac.pt and has active accounts on popular social media platforms like Facebook, Instagram and LinkedIn. Through these channels, the university continuously promotes events and initiatives of the academic community, training opportunities, contests and more.

Furthermore, the Office of Public Relations and Communication regularly sends out emails to both the academic community and the media, disseminating important information and events. Additionally, a newsletter is sent out every Monday, summarizing the key events of the previous week.

By using the highlighted tools and internal services, UAc ensures that all the EXPER CBP actions and outcomes are properly communicated to its internal and external ecosystem.

5.2. ULPGC

To maximize the impact of the CBP, a comprehensive communication strategy will be implemented at ULPGC. This strategy will ensure that all actions and outcomes are effectively communicated both within the university and to external audiences. The communication efforts will leverage the resources and expertise of ULPGC's Communication Office and the Fundación Canaria Parque Científico y Tecnológico de la ULPGC (FCPCT-ULPGC).

Communication Office of ULPGC

The Communication Office at ULPGC is dedicated to managing the university's global communication with transparency and accuracy. Its mission is to disseminate the institution's activities and convey a true image of the university's work to both society and the university community. Acting as a bridge between the university and its surrounding society, the Communication Office establishes channels for effective two-way communication.

In relation to the CBAs implemented by the ULPGC, the Services provided by the Communication Office in line with EXPER's WP7 objectives will include:

- Preparation of press releases and press conference arrangements.
- Creation of promotional and advertising materials for the institution and handling media advertisements.
- Liaison with key stakeholders, including EXPER partners, public and private organizations, institutions, and business leaders.
- The Communication Office will play a central role in promoting the activities and achievements of the CBP, ensuring that all actors, both within and outside the university, are kept informed and engaged.

 FCPCT-ULPGC Dissemination Services

The Fundación Canaria Parque Científico y Tecnológico de la ULPGC (FCPCT-ULPGC) will also be instrumental in the dissemination of the CBP's activities. As the managing body of the EXPER project, the FCPCT-ULPGC is responsible for communicating all events and activities developed under the project, including those related to capacity building and training. These communications will be disseminated through the foundation's social media channels and website, ensuring a broad reach and engagement with the target audiences.

By utilizing the combined resources of the ULPGC Communication Office and FCPCT-ULPGC, the university will ensure that the CBP's impact is effectively communicated to all relevant stakeholders, thereby maximizing the plan's effectiveness and contribution to the university's mission and the broader regional ecosystem.

6. REPORT ON CAPACITY BUILDING ACTIVITIES

This section provides a detailed overview of the CBAs conducted during the project second reporting period (RP2) by both the ULPGC and the UAc. Each activity is documented through descriptive tabular sheets that highlight essential information, including the activity's name, organizers and responsible partners, associated WP, related project activity, number of participants, a general description, etc. These reports aim to provide a comprehensive account of the efforts undertaken to enhance research, innovation, and knowledge transfer capacities at both institutions, ensuring transparency and facilitating the evaluation of the project's impact on the target communities.

6.1. UAC REPORT ON CBAS

Table 21. CBA: Summer School in the Azores

ACTIVITY/EVENT	<i>UAc Summer School: Open Science and Communication, Technology Transfer and Proposal writing for Excellence Research and Innovation</i>
Organizer/Responsible partner/s	UAc
WP	WP4, WP5 and WP7
Associated task/s	Task 4.2 Implementation of Societal Challenges Action Plans, Task 5.1 Capacity building on technology transfer and market-driven activities and Task 7.4 Outreach to citizens, organization and participation in events
Type of participation <i>(organiser, attendee, facilitator, speaker, trainer, etc.)</i>	Activity facilitator and organization: UAc; Attendees: Academia, companies, local authorities, civil society
Number of participants (if applicable)	70
General description of the activity/event and objectives	
<p>The University of the Azores (UAc) held online from September 24th to 26th, 2024, via Microsoft Teams, its EXPER Summer School, tailored for all regional stakeholders in the quadruple helix model, bringing together academia, industry, government, and civil society. This event aimed to enhance participants skills in science communication, technology transfer, and proposal writing.</p> <p>Day 1 - September 24: Science Communication and Open Science</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Introduction to the EXPER Project: Institutional Transformation at UAc and ULPGC, Joint Strategy and Action Plans. - The Role of Science Communication in Scientific Education and the Utilisation of Research Results. - Open Science in Portugal: Concepts, Tools, and Paradigm Shift. <p>Day 2 - September 25: Innovation and Knowledge Transfer</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - From Research to Idea: Support Mechanisms for Technology Transfer. - Case Studies of Regional Companies. <p>Day 3 - September 26: Horizon Europe Proposal Writing</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Opportunities and Best Practices for Horizon Europe Applications. - A Practical Case Study on Proposal Preparation. 	

Through expert presentations, interactive sessions, and insights from and local industry representatives, the event aimed to foster a culture of innovation and effective knowledge transfer, ultimately contributing to societal advancements and economic growth in the ORs.

Tools for the development/implementation of the activity (slides, online presentation, surveys, questionnaires, etc.)

Expert presentations, hands-on practical exercises, tailored slides.

Results, findings, and main conclusions

This event brought together over 70 participants and leading experts from across Europe and national/regional involvement with the UAc to engage in an intensive programme designed to enhance skills in proposal writing, open science and communication, technology transfer and research excellence.

Designed to cultivate project development through group work, the programme enabled participants to collaboratively refine their further development. Three crucial areas of training and expertise were be addressed during the summer school:

- **HE funding opportunities and proposal writing:** Participants gained a better understanding of the available funding sources and opportunities (to the Azores and based on regional S3 strategy) in order for them to make the right choices when applying to EU funding calls, maximizing the regional approval rates and R&D+I in the region. Furthermore, their practical skills on writing successful proposals for Horizon Europe were increased, which results in a raise in competitiveness UAc researchers and their partners and regional stakeholders, contributing to boosting research excellence and ORs participation in EU funding programmes.
- **Improving Science Communication and Open Science practices:** The participants raised their awareness on the importance of science communication and general concepts, good practices and science education to make better use of research results. They also improve their knowledge about open science general concepts, policies/requirements and available tools, data management in open science, the current situation on a national scale, and the opportunities, constraints and challenges in this particular field.
- **Technology Transfer and Innovation:** Through one day dedicated to technology transfer, the project partner ATRINEO conducted a mini-masterclass (which also paved the way for what will be presented on the 2-day workshop to be conducted in Nov/2024) focusing on capacity building on technology transfer and market-driven activities, which aimed to equip participants with the necessary skills and knowledge to bridge the gap between research and practical applications, fostering a culture of innovation and entrepreneurship. This session also included several testimonies of regional companies previously involved with UAc, from the beginning of the knowledge transfer process, through the creation of the companies, typologies of received funding, products and current customers, also giving space to discuss the main obstacles encountered in the companies creation process.

Overall the UAc Summer School contributed the EXPER workpackage's objectives, by provide the participants with the tools and knowledge necessary to drive research excellence, innovation, and effective knowledge transfer, ultimately benefiting both the academic and broader regional communities.

Photographs or other associated documents (if applicable)

Some photos taken during the Summer School (Microsoft Teams):

Table 22. CBA: Workshop on Technology Transfer and Intellectual Property

ACTIVITY/EVENT		<i>Workshop on Technology Transfer and Intellectual Property</i>
Organizer/Responsible partner/s		UAc (InUAc)
WP		WP5 and WP7
Associated task/s		Task 5.1 Capacity building on technology transfer and market-driven activities and Task 7.4 Outreach to citizens, organization and participation in events
Type of participation <i>(organiser, attendee, facilitator, speaker, trainer, etc.)</i>	InUAc (organiser)	
Number of participants (if applicable)	~60	
Date of event	15 April 2024	
General description of the activity/event and objectives		
<p>The Business Incubator of the University of the Azores (InUAc), with the support of the American Corner, within the scope of the activities of the Knowledge Transfer and Enhancement Center, organized a free Workshop with the aim of raising awareness and informing the Academic Community about the importance of issues such as Technology Transfer and Intellectual Property.</p> <p>This workshop was promoted by the Instituto Pedro Nunes (IPN), an entity specialized in this type of subjects. As guest speakers, we had the IPN's Innovation Director, Jorge Pimenta and the Head of Legal of this same organization, José Aguilar.</p> <p>This workshop was meant for the university's incubator's project, for the university's researchers and PhD students. The focus was on technology transfer to the market and on intellectual property, putting into practice the third mission of the Universities: transfer of knowledge to the market.</p>		
Tools for the development/implementation of the activity (slides, online presentation, surveys, questionnaires, etc.)		
Slides, Roll up, online and presential session, questionnaire of satisfaction, certificate of participation.		
Results, findings, and main conclusions		
Awareness of the academy for the theme of valuing and knowledge transfer.		
Photographs or other associated documents (if applicable)		
Some photos taken during the workshop:		

Table 23. CBA: MetaRedX International Exchange Program

ACTIVITY/EVENT	<i>MetaRedX International Exchange Program</i>
Organizer/Responsible partner/s	UAc (InUAc)
WP	WP5
Associated task/s	Task 5.2 Exchanges of staff and good practices on IPR management
Type of participation <i>(organiser, attendee, facilitator, speaker, trainer, etc.)</i>	InUAc (organiser)
Number of participants (if applicable)	~4 (17 Regional Entrepreneurship Ecosystem)
Date of event	27 - 31 May 2024
General description of the activity/event and objectives	
<p>The InUAc (Business Incubator of the University of the Azores) team received a delegation from the Universidad Europea de Madrid, represented by the Director of Employability and Entrepreneurship and the responsible for Entrepreneurship, between 27 and 31 May. This visit took place within the framework of the MetaRedX International Exchange Program, a network that InUAc integrates as a member of the Executive Committee in Portugal and Coordinator of the Entrepreneurship Ecosystems Working Group.</p> <p>The objective of this program was to foster the exchange and sharing of experiences and good practices among the members of the teams of the entrepreneurship management units of the universities that are part of MetaRedX.</p>	

In order to know the work developed by InUAc and the regional entrepreneurship ecosystem, internal meetings were held for the sharing of good practices, as well as meetings with incubators, Mentors, spinoffs, researchers and teachers in the area of UAc entrepreneurship. The articulation with the ecosystem occurred with visits and meetings with NONAGON, the Regional Board of Entrepreneurship and Competitiveness and with the companies Plantation of Tea Gorreana and Algicel.

Tools for the development/implementation of the activity (slides, online presentation, surveys, questionnaires, etc.)

Slides; meetings with incubators, entrepreneurship teachers and researchers; visit to UAc laboratories and research centers; visits to the regional entrepreneurship ecosystem (companies, spinoff UAc, science and technology parks, government/Regional Network of Incubators, etc.).

Results, findings, and main conclusions

It was an excellent opportunity to establish professional contacts, exchange good practices and gain new perspectives to strengthen the entrepreneurial culture in UAc, bringing tangible benefits and promoting sustainable and intelligent development in the Azores.

Photographs or other associated documents (if applicable)

Some photos taken during the program:

Table 24. CBA: Azores Local Creative Jam

ACTIVITY/EVENT		<i>Azores Local Creative Jam</i>
Organizer/Responsible partner/s		UAc (InUAc)
WP		WP5
Associated task/s		Task 5.1 Capacity building on technology transfer and market-driven activities
Type of participation <i>(organiser, attendee, facilitator, speaker, trainer, etc.)</i>	InUAc (organiser, speaker and trainer)	
Number of participants (if applicable)	~16 (young people) 22 (Launch session ATLIC Project)	
Date of event	4 and 5 March 2024	
General description of the activity/event and objectives		
<p>The Local Creative Jam Azores, an intensive event held on 4 and 5 March at the premises of the Business Incubator of the University of the Azores (InUAc) in the Ponta Delgada campus, had as main objective to encourage the young people of the Region to develop skills to identify, in group, new business opportunities in the Blue Economy.</p> <p>Framed in this event, the Launch Session of the ATLIC - Atlantic Innoblue Communities Project took place. InUAc is part of the consortium for this project with the objective of promoting debate on the challenges and opportunities in the Blue Economy. This is a project involving four countries (Ireland, France, Spain and Portugal) and is co-financed by the European Union through the Interreg Atlantic Area Programme.</p> <p>This launch session was attended by the coordinator of InUAc, Deborah Estima, researchers Duarte Toubarro, Maria do Carmo Barreto and Ana Costa from the Faculty of Science and Technology of UAc and the Commercial Director, Marketing and Impact of Futurismo, Carlos Picanço.</p> <p>Workshops in Design Thinking and Business Model were held to work on business ideas and a visit to IS2E - Laboratory of Intelligent Systems, Science and Engineering of UAc. Finally, the participating teams presented their ideas to a jury composed of the InUAc coordinator, the researcher, Duarte Toubarro, the founding partner of Futurismo, Ruben Rodrigues and the Azores DMO coordinator, Carolina Mendonça.</p>		
Tools for the development/implementation of the activity (slides, online presentation, surveys, questionnaires, etc.)		
Slides; Roll Up; presental sessions, questionnaire of satisfaction, certificate of participation		
Results, findings, and main conclusions		
In addition to acquiring these skills, participants will have the opportunity to participate in the International Creative Jam that will be held in Lugo on March 20 and 21. In addition, the winning team was awarded a free year of incubation at InUAc.		
Photographs or other associated documents (if applicable)		
Some photos taken during the event:		

Table 25. CBA: Workshop in Brand Strategy

ACTIVITY/EVENT		<i>Workshop in Brand Strategy</i>
Organizer/Responsible partner/s		UAc (InUAc)
WP		WP5 and WP7
Associated task/s		Task 5.1 Capacity building on technology transfer and market-driven activities and Task 7.4 Outreach to citizens, organization and participation in events
Type of participation <i>(organiser, attendee, facilitator, speaker, trainer, etc.)</i>	Institutional stand: InUAc (organiser)	
Number of participants (if applicable)	~10	
Date of event	22 - 29 November 2023	
General description of the activity/event and objectives		
<p>The Technology Based Business Incubator of the University of the Azores (InUAc), with the support of the American Corner of the University of the Azores, promoted a workshop on Brand Strategy, led by Ricardo Freitas, founder of the company Rebola Caixotes - Brand Expert, that took place at the InUAc Training lab, on the campus of Ponta Delgada, last November.</p> <p>The workshop addressed several topics, focusing on creating a solid brand capable of making an impact in the market. It was attended by 10 trainees, including InUAc incubators and employees of regional companies such as Yoçor and the Marques Group. Throughout the four 12-hour sessions, there was an important exchange of knowledge and ideas among participants, contributing in a relevant way to their current and future business activities.</p>		
Tools for the development/implementation of the activity (slides, online presentation, surveys, questionnaires, etc.)		
Slides, Roll up, online and presential session, questionnaire of satisfaction, certificate of participation.		
Results, findings, and main conclusions		
Trained participants in the area of digital marketing, providing useful tools to implement on a daily basis.		
Photographs or other associated documents (if applicable)		
Some photos taken during the workshop:		

Table 26. CBA: International Meeting of MetaRedX Working Groups

ACTIVITY/EVENT	1st International Meeting of MetaRedX Working Groups
Organizer/Responsible partner/s	UAc (InUAc)
WP	WP5
Associated task/s	Task 5.1 Capacity building on technology transfer and market-driven activities
Type of participation (organiser, attendee, facilitator, speaker, trainer, etc.)	Institutional stand: MetaRedX (organiser) InUAc (participation)
Number of participants (if applicable)	~778
Date of event	9 - 10 October 2023
General description of the activity/event and objectives	

The Business Incubator of the University of the Azores (InUAc) was present at the first face-to-face meeting of the MetaRedX 2023 International Working Groups, organized by MetaRedX by Universia, which was attended by the coordinators of the Working Groups representing 778 Ibero-American Higher Education Institutions belonging to the different MetaRedX networks, including Argentina, Brazil, Chile, Colombia, Spain, Mexico, Peru and Portugal, which took place at the Universidad Panamericana in Mexico City on October 9 and 10.

InUAc's coordinator, Deborah Estima, played an active role in this meeting, leading the Entrepreneurship Ecosystems Working Group in Portugal and the International Entrepreneurship Ecosystems Working Group.

The aim of this meeting was for the different MetaRedX International Working Groups (Entrepreneurship Indicators, Education and Training, Entrepreneurship Ecosystems and Management of Entrepreneurship Units) to define the collaborative projects at international level to be carried out in 2024, thus allowing these projects to have a positive impact on the processes of strengthening the entrepreneurship units of Ibero-American higher education institutions, bringing tangible benefits to the University of the Azores.

Tools for the development/implementation of the activity (slides, online presentation, surveys, questionnaires, etc.)

Slides.

Results, findings, and main conclusions

The activities that will be carried out at international level within the network's Working Groups were outlined, as well as strengthening the bonds of collaboration between the representatives of the eight countries.

Photographs or other associated documents (if applicable)

Some photos taken during the workshop:

6.2. ULPGC REPORT ON CBAS

Table 27. CBA: CLAB Model implementation

ACTIVITY/EVENT	<i>CLAB Model implementation at ULPGC and UAc</i>
Organizer/Responsible partner/s	ULPGC, UAc, EMERGE, UNICAL and CE
WP	WP3
Associated task/s	Task 3.2 Replicating the CLAB model (UNICAL)
Type of participation <i>(organiser, attendee, facilitator, speaker, trainer, etc.)</i>	Activity facilitator: FCPCT-ULPGC & CE; Organization of the activity: ULPGC and UAc; UNICAL and EMERGE: trainers and facilitators.
Number of participants (if applicable)	Variable, depending on the implementation activity, objective and characteristics.
General description of the activity/event and objectives	
<p>One of the pivotal objectives of the EXPER project is to enhance the research and innovation capacities of Widening universities located in the ORs of the EU, such as the University of the Azores (UAc) and the University of Las Palmas de Gran Canaria (ULPGC). The CLAB model implementation at ULPGC and UAc seeks to strengthen the role of these institutions as drivers of economic and social transformation in their respective territories.</p> <p>As part of the project's WP3, which focuses on attracting and retaining talent within these universities, one of the key objectives is to implement the CLAB model. This model, already in place at leading European universities like the University of Calabria (UNICAL), aims to foster entrepreneurship and innovation among students and recent graduates from various disciplines. The CLAB ULPGC project is designed to nurture the talent of participants by placing them in diverse teams, supported by specialized mentors, and adopting new learning methodologies, such as Lean methodology. Participants will develop skills in problem-solving, decision-making, teamwork, project management, oral communication, and business planning, all aimed at creating a viable business idea.</p> <p>The CLAB ULPGC project includes both theoretical and practical training activities, such as:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Business idea challenges, meetings, conferences, and team-building sessions outside conventional university settings. <p>As part of the CLAB Model implementation at ULPGC, experts from the University of Calabria (UNICAL) held a training meeting with mentors from ULPGC to provide specialized training on the development and implementation of the CLAB model. Drawing from their extensive experience with the model at UNICAL, the experts guided ULPGC mentors through the core methodologies and strategies needed to successfully adapt and apply the CLAB model within the context of ULPGC. This preparatory phase was essential in ensuring the effective launch and sustainability of the CLAB project at ULPGC. Furthermore, the theoretical part of the training is being conducted at the ULPGC's Tafira Campus, specifically at the NEXO building, the ULPGC Science and Technology Park Foundation, and/or other specific teaching facilities of the university.</p> <p>The CLAB ULPGC project is structured into four phases:</p> <p>Phase 0: Promotion and Submission of Applications</p>	

Phase 1: Academy (June-July 2024) - This phase involves group workshops with specialized guidance, applying the training content to specific start-up projects. For individual candidates without an initial business idea, the first phase will focus on developing a business idea collaboratively with other participants in the same situation, forming diverse groups of up to five members.

Phase 2: Pre-Acceleration (September-November 2024) - Group work to develop an action plan through individual mentorship aimed at advancing the business development process.

Phase 3: Final Contest (December 2024) - This phase includes pitch sessions where project ideas are presented to both internal and external audiences, followed by the selection of the most promising entrepreneurial project. The winning group will have the opportunity to participate in an exchange program with the University of Calabria in Italy, where they can further develop their project.

The implementation of the CLAB model at ULPGC is currently ongoing and progressing according to the planned schedule of activities.

Tools for the development/implementation of the activity (slides, online presentation, surveys, questionnaires, etc.)

Microsoft Teams and onsite meetings, onsite/online classes, online presentations, elements of dynamization, schedules, AI tools, etc.

Results, findings, and main conclusions

The implementation of the CLAB model at the ULPGC is anticipated to yield significant outcomes that align with the overarching goals of the EXPER project. By fostering entrepreneurship and innovation, the CLAB model is expected to enhance the university's role as a catalyst for economic and social transformation in the Canary Islands. The following key results and objectives are projected:

- **Enhanced Entrepreneurial Ecosystem:** The CLAB model aims to strengthen the entrepreneurial ecosystem within ULPGC by equipping students and recent graduates with the skills and knowledge needed to create viable business ventures. Through hands-on experience and mentorship, participants will develop the capacity to navigate the challenges of entrepreneurship, contributing to the growth of start-ups and innovation-driven businesses in the region.
- **Development of crucial competencies:** Participants in the CLAB ULPGC project are expected to acquire essential skills such as problem-solving, decision-making, teamwork, project management, and business planning. These competencies are critical for the successful development and execution of entrepreneurial projects, and their cultivation will prepare participants for leadership roles in the business and innovation sectors.
- **Creation of innovative Start-Ups:** One of the primary objectives of the CLAB model is to facilitate the creation of innovative start-ups by students and graduates. The structured phases of the project, from idea generation to business plan development and final pitch presentations, are designed to support the emergence of new business ventures that can contribute to the economic diversification of the Canary Islands.
- **Strengthened University-Industry collaboration:** By engaging with executives, entrepreneurs, investors, and other key players in the entrepreneurial and innovation ecosystem, the CLAB model is expected to foster stronger ties between ULPGC and the business community. This collaboration will not only provide participants with valuable insights and opportunities but also enhance the university's capacity to contribute to regional economic development.
- **Increased regional economic impact:** The successful implementation of the CLAB model is projected to have a positive impact on the regional economy. By nurturing innovative start-ups and fostering a culture of entrepreneurship, ULPGC will play a crucial role in driving economic growth, creating jobs, and promoting sustainable development in the Canary Islands.
- **Promotion of a Culture of Innovation:** The CLAB model aims to embed a culture of innovation within ULPGC by encouraging participants to think creatively and pursue new ideas. This cultural shift is expected to extend beyond the immediate participants of the program, influencing the broader university community and contributing to a more dynamic and innovative academic environment.

- Enhanced International collaboration:** The exchange program with the University of Calabria, which is part of the final phase of the CLAB project, is expected to strengthen international collaboration and provide participants with a global perspective on entrepreneurship and innovation. This experience will further enhance the quality and impact of the projects developed at ULPGC.
- Contribution to the EXPER Project Goals:** Ultimately, the implementation of the CLAB model at ULPGC is aligned with the broader objectives of the EXPER project (Task 3.2), particularly in enhancing the research and innovation capacities of Widening universities in the EU's ORs. By achieving these results, ULPGC will reinforce its position as a leading institution in the Canary Islands, capable of driving significant economic and social advancements.

The CLAB model's integration into ULPGC is anticipated to serve as a transformative initiative, equipping the university and its stakeholders with the tools and resources needed to thrive in a rapidly evolving global economy.

Photographs or other associated documents (if applicable)

Some photos of the activities conducted during the implementation of the CLAB model at ULPGC so far:

Table 28. CBA: Colloquium on Innovation and internationalisation with ICEX Director

ACTIVITY/EVENT	<i>Colloquium on Innovation and internationalisation with ICEX Director</i>
Organizer/Responsible partner/s	FCPCT, ULPGC
WP	WP5 and WP7
Associated task/s	Task 5.1 Capacity building on technology transfer and market-driven activities and Task 7.4 Outreach to citizens, organization and participation in events
Type of participation <i>(organiser, attendee, facilitator, speaker, trainer, etc.)</i>	Activity facilitator: FCPCT; Organization of the activity: ULPGC
Number of participants (if applicable)	28
General description of the activity/event and objectives	

As part of the EXPER project initiatives in the Canary Islands, startups and businesses within the entrepreneurial ecosystem of the University of Las Palmas de Gran Canaria (ULPGC) engaged in a productive dialogue with José María Blasco Ruiz, Director of Infrastructures, Health, and ICT at ICEX. This event, aligning with WP5 focused on business environment connection and knowledge transfer, and WP7 focused on outreach, was held to foster interaction between the university's spin-offs and ICEX's internationalization initiatives.

During the colloquium, Blasco shared valuable insights into ICEX's initiatives supporting entrepreneurship, innovation, and internationalization. He highlighted opportunities such as participation in international fairs, commercial missions, and the [Desafía programme](#), which offers a two-week immersion in diverse multi-sector destinations like San Francisco, Berlin, London, Singapore, and the Nordic countries. These initiatives aim to enhance the global reach and scalability of startups.

The event, chaired by ULPGC's Vice-Rector for Research and Transfer, Sebastián López, and led by María José Miranda, Director of Scientific Infrastructures and Relations with Companies at ULPGC, emphasized the importance of international market opportunities for the university's entrepreneurial ventures. The discussion also involved key participants such as Loreto Taborga, Territorial Director of Commerce and ICEX Delegate in Las Palmas, and María Josefa Padrón, Managing Director of the Canarian Foundation Science and Technology Park of ULPGC, where the colloquium took place on February 21 (2024).

The primary objective of this activity was to strengthen the connection between the entrepreneurial ecosystem associated with ULPGC and ICEX, with the aim of providing entrepreneurs, start-ups, spin-offs and other stakeholders in the Canary Islands region with firsthand knowledge of the resources and opportunities that ICEX offers in this field.

Tools for the development/implementation of the activity (slides, online presentation, surveys, questionnaires, etc.)

On-site meeting, tailored slides, institutional facilitators and representatives, open colloquium.

Results, findings, and main conclusions

The ICEX colloquium with the ULPGC entrepreneurial ecosystem strengthened the connection between local startups and spin-offs with ICEX resources, highlighting international opportunities and support programs like "Desafía". Participants gained key information about participation criteria and showed increased interest in engaging with ICEX initiatives.

Photographs or other associated documents (if applicable)

Some photos taken during the Colloquium with ICEX:

Table 29. CBA: Staff Exchange with KIT (Karlsruhe Institute of Technology)

ACTIVITY/EVENT		<i>Staff Exchange with KIT (Karlsruhe Institute of Technology)</i>
Organizer/Responsible partner/s		FCPCT-ULPGC, ATRINEO
WP		WP5
Associated task/s		Task 5.2 Exchanges of staff and good practices on IPR management
Type of participation <i>(organiser, attendee, facilitator, speaker, trainer, etc.)</i>	Activity facilitator and organization: FCPCT-ULPGC, ATRINEO. Attendee: ITC	
Number of participants (if applicable)	4	
General description of the activity/event and objectives		
<p>From June 12 to June 13, 2024, a delegation from the University of Las Palmas de Gran Canaria (ULPGC) visited the Karlsruhe Institute of Technology (KIT) in Germany to explore KIT's pioneering work in knowledge transfer, particularly within the realms of innovation and sustainability. The visit was strategically aligned with the "Innovation Day in Neuland" event at KIT, which emphasized innovations contributing to a greener, more digital, and healthier future in line with the EU's sustainability goals. The ULPGC delegation, participating under the Exper project, included representatives from the university's Knowledge Transfer Office (OTC), ITC (Instituto Tecnológico de Canarias), and ATRINEO AG. The exchange focused on sharing best practices in intellectual property rights (IPR) management and exploring potential future collaborations between ULPGC and KIT.</p> <p>The principal objectives of this activity were to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Provide ULPGC's delegation with exposure to cutting-edge research and innovative practices at KIT, thereby informing and improving their own knowledge transfer initiatives. 		
Tools for the development/implementation of the activity (slides, online presentation, surveys, questionnaires, etc.)		
On-site meetings, oral presentations, innovation event.		
Results, findings, and main conclusions		
<p>The visit to KIT provided valuable insights into several of its key initiatives. The intrapreneurship program at KIT, which focuses on maximizing the impact of each employee, was particularly noteworthy. This program not only facilitates knowledge transfer but also empowers employees to influence various dimensions, including basic research. The TRIANGEL initiative was another highlight, offering a versatile</p>		

space that serves both entrepreneurs and the public, fostering citizen science and science dissemination. However, it was noted that the initiative currently faces staffing challenges.

The relationship between KIT and local companies, bolstered by a strong alumni network, stood out as a significant advantage. In contrast to the Canary Islands, where connections between researchers and companies often rely on intermediary organizations, the collaborations in Karlsruhe are more organic and spontaneous. This difference underscores the varying levels of innovation maturity between the two regions, with Karlsruhe being an "innovation leader" and the Canary Islands an "emerging" region.

Overall, the exchange reinforced the importance of strategic collaboration, the role of innovation spaces, and the potential of tailored intrapreneurship programs. It also highlighted the need for ULPGC to explore similar initiatives to enhance its own innovation ecosystem and strengthen ties between academia and industry.

Photographs or other associated documents (if applicable)

Some photos taken during the staff exchange with KIT:

Table 30. CBA: Training Workshop by ATRINEO – From Research to Idea

ACTIVITY/EVENT	<i>Training Workshop by ATRINEO – From Research to Idea</i>
Organizer/Responsible partner/s	FCPCT-ULPGC, ATRINEO
WP	WP5
Associated task/s	Task 5.1 Capacity building on technology transfer and market-driven activities
Type of participation <i>(organiser, attendee, facilitator, speaker, trainer, etc.)</i>	Activity facilitator and organization: FCPCT-ULPGC; Trainer: ATRINEO and ITC. Attendee: ITC, CE
Number of participants (if applicable)	June session: 15; July session: 9
General description of the activity/event and objectives	

As part of the ongoing activities within the EXPER Project, two training sessions titled “De la Investigación a la Idea” (From Research to Idea) were conducted under Task 5.1, focusing on capacity building in technology transfer and market-driven activities. Given the high number of initial registrations, the training was offered in two editions. The first edition took place on June 19 and 20, 2024, and the second on July 10 and 11, 2024. Both sessions were held at the Polyvalent II Building, Floor 0, Aula de Formación Sala Polivalente 1 at FCPCT-ULPGC.

The training, delivered by the project partner ATRINEO, was designed for research staff from the University of Las Palmas de Gran Canaria (ULPGC), concerned stakeholders of the surrounding community and other project members. The comprehensive agenda spanned two days and covered critical topics such as understanding innovation from a scientific perspective, identifying success factors in scientific innovation, and generating ideas from market challenges.

Day 1 focused on mapping the road to innovation, emphasizing market orientation, and prioritizing opportunities through market analysis. Day 2 delved into validating innovations, market analysis techniques, defining and segmenting markets, and the fundamentals of creating startups and business models from scientific ventures. Practical sessions were incorporated throughout to ensure hands-on experience.

The primary objective of these workshops was to equip participants with the necessary skills and knowledge to bridge the gap between research and practical applications, thereby fostering a culture of innovation and entrepreneurship within the EXPER project and the broader academic community of the ULPGC.

Tools for the development/implementation of the activity (slides, online presentation, surveys, questionnaires, etc.)

On-site meeting, oral presentations, hands-on practical exercises, tailored slides, post-event satisfaction questionnaires.

Results, findings, and main conclusions

The “From Research to Idea” training sessions yielded significant, aligning closely with the core objectives of the EXPER Project. Participants demonstrated a marked improvement in their understanding of the technology transfer process, particularly in how to translate research outcomes into viable market-driven innovations. This training was instrumental in enhancing the capacity of ULPGC’s research personnel to engage in effective knowledge and technology transfer, a key objective of the project.

One of the most notable outcomes was the participants’ ability to apply practical tools for market analysis and business model creation, which are essential for bridging the gap between academic research and industry needs. The interactive nature of the sessions, with hands-on exercises and real-world examples, enabled participants to better grasp the complexities of innovation and entrepreneurship. This, in turn, has the potential to significantly enhance ULPGC’s role in contributing to societal advancement through impactful research and innovation.

The high level of engagement and positive feedback from the participants underscored the importance of continuing such training initiatives. These sessions not only fulfilled the immediate educational goals but also laid a strong foundation for future capacity-building efforts, ensuring that ULPGC remains a leading institution in fostering innovation and facilitating the transfer of knowledge and technologies to the broader community.

Photographs or other associated documents (if applicable)

Some photos taken during the training workshop:

Table 31. CBA: Summer School in Gran Canaria

ACTIVITY/EVENT		<i>Summer School in Gran Canaria: Open Science and Writing Successful Projects for Excellent Research and Disruptive Innovation: Horizon Europe 2021-2027, ERC (European Research Council) & EIC (European Innovation Council).</i>
Organizer/Responsible partner/s		ULPGC, FCPCT-ULPGC, CE and ITC
WP		WP3, WP4 and WP5
Associated task/s		Task 4.2 Implementation of Societal Challenges Action Plans
Type of participation <i>(organiser, attendee, facilitator, speaker, trainer, etc.)</i>	Activity facilitator and organization: ULPGC, FCPCT-ULPGC, CE and ITC; Attendee: UAc	
Number of participants (if applicable)	126	
General description of the activity/event and objectives		
<p>The EXPER Project's Summer School, held at the University of Las Palmas de Gran Canaria (ULPGC) from July 17 to July 19, 2024, aimed to strengthen research proposal writing skills and enhance the impact of research at ULPGC and the University of the Azores (UAc). This event was designed to promote excellent and responsible research practices, with a focus on Horizon Europe, European Research Council (ERC), and European Innovation Council (EIC) funding opportunities.</p> <p>Participants engaged in an intensive programme covering three main training areas:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Day Two. ERC Proposals and Open Science: Enhancing researchers' abilities to secure ERC grants by setting ambitious research objectives and embracing open science practices. 		

- 🌐 Day Three. EIC Funding for Startups and Spin-offs: Exploring EIC funding instruments and their role in supporting innovative ventures, particularly in Europe's ORs.

The Summer School also featured hands-on practical workshops on Horizon Europe proposal writing, involving international and multidisciplinary collaboration. Through expert presentations, interactive sessions, and insights from local industry representatives, the event aimed to foster a culture of innovation and effective knowledge transfer, ultimately contributing to societal advancements and economic growth in the ORs.

Tools for the development/implementation of the activity (slides, online presentation, surveys, questionnaires, etc.)

On-site meetings, oral presentations, hands-on practical exercises, tailored slides, post-event satisfaction questionnaires.

Results, findings, and main conclusions

The EXPER Project's Summer School in Gran Canaria returned significant results and excellent participants' feedback, aligning closely with the project's objectives of enhancing research excellence and fostering innovation within the ULPGC and UAc communities. Below, the pivotal ones are underscored:

- 🌐 **Strengthened proposal writing skills:** Participants gained practical knowledge and refined their abilities to craft successful proposals for Horizon Europe and ERC funding. This is crucial for increasing the competitiveness of researchers from ULPGC and UAc in securing EU grants, directly contributing to the project's aim of boosting research excellence in peripheral regions.
- 🌐 **Enhanced knowledge of EU funding opportunities:** The sessions on ERC and EIC programmes provided participants with a deep understanding of available funding instruments, enabling them to better navigate the large landscape of EU research funding. This knowledge is essential for advancing high-impact research and innovation projects.
- 🌐 **Promotion and real application of Open Science practices:** The focus on open science and research evaluation underscored the importance of transparency, collaboration, and accessibility in research, aligning with the project's commitment to responsible research practices.
- 🌐 **Increased collaboration and networking:** The Summer School facilitated valuable connections between researchers, industry representatives, and other stakeholders. These networks are vital for fostering collaboration, which is a key component of successful knowledge and technology transfer—a core objective of the EXPER project.
- 🌐 **Support for Startups and Spin-offs:** By addressing the specific needs of startups and spin-offs, particularly in relation to EIC funding, the event helped lay the groundwork for translating research into market-driven innovations. This directly supports the project's goal of enhancing the region's innovation ecosystem.

Overall, the Summer School significantly contributed to the EXPER Project's mission by equipping participants with the tools and knowledge necessary to drive research excellence, innovation, and effective knowledge transfer, ultimately benefiting both the academic and broader regional communities.

Photographs or other associated documents (if applicable)

Some photos taken during the Summer School in Gran Canaria:

Table 32. CBA: Training Workshop by SPEGC – Support Tools to incentivize and promote University-Business collaboration through R&D&I Taxation.

ACTIVITY/EVENT		<i>Training Workshop by SPEGC – Support Tools to incentivize and promote University-Business collaboration through R&D&I Taxation</i>
Organizer/Responsible partner/s		ULPGC, FCPCT-ULPGC, SPEGC
WP		WP6
Associated task/s		Task 6.3 Feasibility studies and partnership agreement for establishment of spin-offs supporting offices
Type of participation <i>(organiser, attendee, facilitator, speaker, trainer, etc.)</i>	Activity facilitator and organization: ULPGC, FCPCT-ULPGC; Trainer: SPEGC	
Number of participants (if applicable)	10	
General description of the activity/event and objectives		
<p>The Economic Promotion Agency of Gran Canaria (SPEGC) recently hosted a pioneering training session aimed at strengthening university-business collaboration, as part of WP6 of the EXPER Project. This inaugural session, titled “Support Tools to Incentivize and Promote University-Business Collaboration through R&D&I Taxation,” was specifically designed to equip leading researchers and administrative staff from the University of Las Palmas de Gran Canaria (ULPGC) with the knowledge and tools necessary to enhance collaboration between academia and industry.</p> <p>Taking place on June 13, 2024, at the facilities of the FCPCT-ULPGC, the session served as a pilot initiative under Task 6.3 of the EXPER project. The primary objective was to introduce key stakeholders within ULPGC to the basic principles of R&D&I tax instruments and their potential to incentivize collaborative research and innovation projects between universities and businesses.</p> <p>The session's agenda was carefully structured to provide a comprehensive overview within a concise timeframe, covering essential topics such as:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Basic Principles of R&D&I Tax Instruments (25 minutes): A foundational understanding of the tax incentives available for research, development, and innovation. 		

- 🌐 Use Cases Focused on University-Business Collaboration (25 minutes): Practical examples illustrating how tax instruments can effectively support collaboration.
- 🌐 Additional Tools and Actions to Promote Business Collaboration (15 minutes): Exploration of other mechanisms and strategies to foster partnerships.
- 🌐 Action Planning and Conclusions (30 minutes): Discussion and planning for the implementation of these tools within the university's collaborative efforts.

The session brought together key figures from the EXPER project coordination team and SPEGC, including Almudena Suárez, Financial Manager of the EXPER Project and Head of the European Projects Office at ULPGC-FCPCT, María José Miranda Martel, Director of Scientific Infrastructures at ULPGC, Tanausú Dávila, Project Manager of the EXPER Project, Cosme García Falcón, Managing Director of SPEGC, and Juan Ramón Rodríguez, Economic Promotion Technician at SPEGC.

This initiative represents a crucial step in fostering stronger ties between academia and industry in Gran Canaria, leveraging fiscal tools to stimulate innovation and collaborative research. By providing participants with practical knowledge and actionable strategies, the session aims to build a foundation for ongoing and future collaborations that will drive regional economic growth and enhance the impact of research at ULPGC.

Tools for the development/implementation of the activity (slides, online presentation, surveys, questionnaires, etc.)

On-site meetings, oral presentations, hands-on practical exercises, tailored slides, post-event satisfaction questionnaires.

Results, findings, and main conclusions

The training session hosted by SPEGC on “Support Tools to Incentivize and Promote University-Business Collaboration through R&D&I Taxation” yielded significant outcomes, aligning closely with the principal objectives of the EXPER Project.

- 🌐 **Enhanced awareness of R&D&I Tax instruments:** Participants gained a deeper understanding of the various fiscal tools available to support research, development, and innovation (R&D&I) through university-business collaborations. This knowledge is crucial for enabling researchers and administrative staff at ULPGC to effectively leverage these incentives, thereby fostering more productive and impactful partnerships with the private sector.
- 🌐 **Practical application:** The session's use case studies provided concrete examples of how tax instruments can be applied to real-world collaborations. This practical approach not only clarified theoretical concepts but also equipped participants with the tools needed to implement these strategies in their own projects, enhancing the potential for successful outcomes.
- 🌐 **Action-Oriented planning:** The final part of the session focused on action planning, ensuring that participants left with a clear understanding of the next steps required to apply the knowledge gained. This strategic focus is essential for translating training into tangible results, driving the long-term success of collaborative initiatives.
- 🌐 **Foundation for future training and expansion:** As a pilot initiative, the session laid the groundwork for future trainings that will expand the reach of this knowledge to a broader audience within ULPGC and its partners. The positive reception and engagement of participants underscore the need for ongoing capacity building in this area, which is critical for achieving the EXPER Project's goals of enhancing research excellence and fostering regional innovation.

This training session directly supports the EXPER Project's objectives by equipping ULPGC staff with the skills and knowledge necessary to strengthen the university's ties with the business community. By promoting the use of fiscal tools to incentivize collaboration, the event contributes to building a more robust innovation ecosystem in Gran Canaria. Moreover, the focus on practical implementation aligns with the project's goal of transforming research into actionable, market-driven solutions, ultimately driving economic growth and societal impact.

In summary, this session represents a significant step forward in achieving the EXPER Project's mission of fostering excellence in research and enhancing the capacity for knowledge and technology transfer at

ULPGC. The outcomes of this event will serve as a catalyst for further development in university-business collaborations, setting the stage for continued progress and innovation within the region.

Photographs or other associated documents (if applicable)

Some photos taken during the training session conducted by SPEGC:

7. CONCLUSIONS

The implementation of the CBP within the EXPER Project is set to play a pivotal role in advancing the strategic objectives of both the ULPGC and the UAc. This plan will not only serve as a cornerstone for enhancing research excellence and fostering innovation but will also position these institutions as key drivers of economic growth and regional development in their respective areas. These areas are highlighted below to emphasize the key results to be achieved.

- **Strengthening Research and Innovation capacities:** The CBP is expected to significantly bolster the research and innovation capabilities of ULPGC and UAc. Through targeted training sessions, such as those focusing on Horizon Europe proposal writing, R&D&I tax incentives, and university-business collaboration, researchers and administrative staff are to acquire critical skills and knowledge. These initiatives will empower the institutions to better navigate and capitalize on European funding opportunities, leading to increased research output and more robust participation in high-impact projects.

-
- **Enhancing University-Business collaboration:** A key outcome anticipated from the CBP is the strengthened collaboration between universities and the private sector. By equipping participants with tools to leverage fiscal incentives and create synergies with industry, the plan is expected to facilitate the development of partnerships that are essential for translating research into market-driven innovations. This alignment with industry needs will not only enhance the practical impact of academic research but also contribute directly to regional economic growth.

 - **Regional economic development:** The CBAs are expected to underscore the critical role of ULPGC and UAc as catalysts for regional development. By enhancing the institutions' ability to drive innovation and foster collaboration with local industries, the plan will contribute to creating a more dynamic and competitive regional economy. The skills and knowledge acquired through the EXPER Project are anticipated to have long-lasting effects, enabling these universities to continue to serve as engines of economic growth and development in their regions.

 - **Building a sustainable future:** The CBP is designed to lay a strong foundation for the sustainable development of research and innovation ecosystems in the Canary Islands and the Azores. By fostering a culture of continuous learning and adaptation, the plan will ensure that ULPGC and UAc are well-equipped to meet future challenges and opportunities. The emphasis on open science, responsible research practices, and strategic funding alignment will continue to drive the institutions' contributions to societal and economic advancements.

 - **Achieving Project objectives:** The successful implementation of the CBP is crucial for achieving the overarching goals of the EXPER Project. By enhancing the capacities of ULPGC and UAc, the project aims to strengthen their roles as key players in the European Research Area. The institutions will be better positioned to lead and participate in international research collaborations, drive innovation, and contribute to the economic prosperity of their regions.

In conclusion, the CBP is expected to be a vital component of the EXPER Project, delivering tangible benefits to both ULPGC and UAc. It will not only advance the research and innovation capabilities of these institutions but also reinforce their roles as central to the economic development of their regions. The knowledge and skills developed through this plan are anticipated to yield positive outcomes, ensuring that ULPGC and UAc remain at the forefront of regional and European research and innovation efforts.

8. ANNEX

This section includes additional documents relevant in the context of this report, providing support and further details to the topics discussed. Below are the annexed elements included:

- Catalogue of Best Practices from the University of Rostock: This document compiles a series of best practices implemented at the University of Rostock (UROS) that have proven effective in enhancing research and innovation capabilities. This catalogue serves as a key reference for identifying potential models and strategies that can be adapted and implemented in Widening universities such as ULPGC and UAc.
- KPI Tracking record and Monitoring Templates for ULPGC and UAc: These templates have been designed to facilitate the tracking and evaluation of the Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) defined in the Capacity Building Plan (CBP) for both universities. Their use will allow the institutions to effectively monitor the

progress of the established actions, thereby ensuring the achievement of the objectives of the EXPER project.

These documents provide a solid foundation for the implementation of effective practices, on one hand, and the continuous evaluation of the results to be achieved at the participating universities by implementing the CBPs, on the other hand.

Best practices for promoting scientific and economic capacities at the University of Rostock

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1 DIVERSITY MANAGEMENT

1.1 DIVERSITY OFFICE

The Diversity Office supports the strategic development of the university in the overarching fields of diversity management and equal opportunities, welcoming culture, inclusion and accessibility, health management, family friendliness, and equality and, since the end of 2020, sustainability development. The “KarriereWegeMentoring” (Career Path Mentoring) project is also part of the staff unit and provides targeted support for (young) female scientists.

1.2 GENDER EQUALITY OFFICE

The Equal Opportunities Officer supports the management and the central bodies of the University of Rostock in fulfilling their legal mandate to promote the actual implementation of equal rights for women and men and to work towards the elimination of existing disadvantages - especially for women in science.

Furthermore, the Equal Opportunity Officer advises, informs and supports all university members in reconciling study/work and family and accompanies the enforcement of the General Equal Treatment Act with regard to protection against discrimination on the grounds of gender and sexual harassment.

1.3 INCLUSION ACTION PLANS

Students with disabilities or chronic illnesses in particular are still confronted with study and learning conditions that take their individual needs into account only to a limited extent or not at all in everyday university life.

Against the background of the Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities (CRPD) of the United Nations (2006) inclusive university teaching aims at the development and implementation of barrier-free study structures and barrier-free teaching offers.

1.4 FAMILY OFFICE

A scientific qualification means fixed-term contracts and often a double burden. How can the compatibility of family and science be achieved? What do scientists who want to pursue an academic career with children have to consider? We would like to support you in finding the right information and advice for you from the existing offers on the topic of reconciling science and family.

2 RESEARCHER SUPPORT

2.1 UNIVERSITY HEALTH MANAGEMENT

The “URgesund” steering committee is the central steering and decision-making body of university health management. The goal is to initiate and support health-promoting working and living conditions at the University of Rostock. The main task is to create and establish information offers and measures in the field of health in order to maintain and promote the well-being and health of employees and students at the University of Rostock. “URgesund” advise on the strategic orientation as well as financial and legal issues that arise in this context.

2.2 FEMALE MENTORING PROGRAM

The focus here is on supporting female doctoral students in their orientation toward a further career in science or a professional career in business, industry, public administration or associations.

The special focus of the mentoring program is on one-to-one mentoring, i.e., each mentee is individually accompanied by a mentor in her personal career planning. In addition, a high-quality seminar program is offered on topics such as self-marketing and career planning. The two networking events on "Successful Careers" and "Research Funding" focus on connecting with established women in order to share in and benefit from their experiences. In peer mentoring, mentees work on self-determined topics in a peer group of 5 to 6 mentees. They support each other effectively and deal intensively with their own goals and progress. For this purpose, the mentees learn the method of "collegial consultation". This results in a non-competitive exchange at a very high level, which also benefits from the fact that the mentees come from different disciplines.

2.3 WELCOME CENTRE FOR FOREIGN RESEARCHERS

The Welcome Center / Global Café supports and advises foreign doctoral candidates and visiting scientists. Here they can obtain information on topics such as work permits, immigration law and language courses. The services offered by the Welcome Center also include help with filling out forms and support in finding accommodation.

2.4 GRADUATE ACADEMY

The university-wide Graduate Academy is the central service institution and coordination point for young scientists.

The central goal of the Graduate Academy is to support and promote young scientists at the University of Rostock. The range of services includes the qualification program, funding offers for participation in external qualification measures, travel allowances and various networking opportunities. The qualification program serves the further

development of interdisciplinary competences in a conscious and intrinsically motivated way. Members of the Graduate Academy can use their budget, which is made available to them by the Graduate Academy, for the fee-based courses. Members of the Graduate Academy can use up to 500 EUR of their membership budget for travel grants. In addition, the Graduate Academy is the contact point for all questions and concerns regarding young scientists. We see accompanying, advising and informing as our elementary basis. We focus on the needs of our addressees - the young scientists.

2.5 GRADUATE SCHOOLS

Graduate schools are structured doctoral programs funded in Germany by the German Research Foundation (DFG). These programs promote interdisciplinary research projects and offer doctoral students' intensive supervision and a broad range of qualification measures.

Graduate schools offer doctoral students an intensive research environment and the opportunity to work in an interdisciplinary team. The doctorate in a Research Training Group is usually scheduled for three to four years and, in addition to the actual research work, also includes a variety of qualification measures, such as workshops, colloquia and summer schools.

Current research focus areas at the University of Rostock are: Smart Appliance Ensembles for Mobile Applications, Interactions between Implants and Biosystems or Smart Appliance Ensembles for Mobile Applications. However, any other subject areas can also be funded.

3 RESEARCHER TRAINING AND SKILL ENHANCEMENT

3.1 ONLINE LEARNING PLATFORM

The online learning portal offers an interdisciplinary selection of online learning opportunities on a wide range of topics. It distinguishes between short micro-lectures, video lectures and complex online courses with exercises and tests. The educational offer of the open University of Rostock is aimed, among others, at professionals, teachers, companies, project partners and students

Examples:

- Project management
- Patent protection for start-ups
- Bogs - an introduction

3.2 SCIENTIFIC QUALIFICATION COURSES

The qualification program serves the further development of interdisciplinary competences in a conscious and intrinsically motivated way. It targets PhD students of the university. Topics are among others academic writing, reading, project management and disputation training.

3.3 DIDACTIC CERTIFICATE OF THE UNIVERSITY OF ROSTOCK

The University Didactics of the University of Rostock supports teachers of the University of Rostock and of universities and colleges in the state of MV in their competence development and continuing education. The portfolio of events in higher education didactics offers workshops that are designed to meet the current needs of teaching and provide a framework for interdisciplinary exchange. Through a practical approach, the participants are able to apply the knowledge gained directly in their own teaching.

4 SCHOLARSHIPS AND RESEARCH FUNDING

4.1 PHD STUDENTS

- Financing of external qualification measures - funding offer for members of the Graduate Academy
- HERMES Funding: supports research stays of young scientists abroad that are linked to an application for third-party funding
- “KarriereWegeMentoring” - support program for female doctoral students ([see 2.2](#))
- State Graduate Support - Doctoral Scholarship Program for Graduates with Outstanding Achievements
- Open Access Publication Fund - Fund for the financial support of open access publications
- Female professors' program: Equal opportunity measures (scholarships, material grants, fund for student assistants) for the promotion of young female researchers
- Doctoral scholarship program "Our best masters do their doctorate in Rostock" - Doctoral scholarship program for the best master's graduates
- Travel allowances for participation in symposia - Support for members of the Graduate Academy
- Bridging, reintegration and graduation scholarships for junior researchers - Scholarships for junior researchers with extensive family responsibilities

4.2 POSTDOCS

- Funding of external qualification measures - funding offer for members of the Graduate Academy
- HERMES research funding - funding for research stays abroad
- “Impuls Forschung” - start-up financing of research cooperations of the member universities in the Association of North German Universities (VNU)
- “KarriereWegeMentoring” - Strengthening of young female scientists on their career path ([see 2.2](#))
- Open Access Publication Fund - Fund for the financial support of open access publications
- Program for female professors: Equal opportunity measures (scholarships, material grants, funds for student assistants) for the promotion of young female researchers
- Travel allowances for participation in symposia - Support offered by the Graduate Academy
- Scholarships for bridging, reintegration and graduation scholarships for junior researchers - Scholarships for junior researchers with extensive family responsibilities to complete their qualification phase

4.3 JUNIOR PROFESSORS

- “Impuls Forschung” - start-up funding for research cooperation of the member universities in the Association of North German Universities (VNU)
- Open Access Publication Fund - financial support for open access publications in journals
- Program for female professors: equal opportunity measures (scholarships, material grants, funds for student assistants) for the promotion of young female researchers
- Program for Female Professors:
 - advancing the equality of women and men at universities,
 - a sustainable improvement in the representation of women at all levels of qualification in the science system, and
 - increasing the number of female scientists in top positions in the scientific field.

4.4 “SOCIETY OF PROMOTERS OF THE UNIVERSITY OF ROSTOCK “

The “Society of Promoters of the University of Rostock” (“Gesellschaft der Förderer der Universität Rostock”) was founded to give members, graduates and friends of the

university, politicians and representatives from business, science and culture the opportunity to help stimulate the development of the university.

For example, the sponsoring society awards up to three University of Rostock sponsorship prizes annually for outstanding dissertations defended at the University of Rostock. In addition, a sponsorship prize for teaching is awarded annually.

5 RESEARCH PROJECTS

5.1 PROJECTS SERVICE CENTER

The team of strategic research consulting advises and accompanies members of the university on research programs that are particularly relevant to higher education policy, such as EU Horizon Europe (especially ERC grants), as well as DFG Collaborative Research Centers and Research Training Groups.

The Project Administration team combines all services provided by Central University Administration related to the administrative processes of acquiring, accepting, managing, and closing projects.

5.2 INFORMATION PLATFORM FOR EXTERNAL FUNDED PROJECTS

The research database is a platform of the University of Rostock, through which information on third-party funded projects, doctorates and postdoctoral theses as well as scientific publications at the University of Rostock can be searched.

In addition, national third-party funders are presented online. In addition, current calls for proposals for funding programs are presented in funding news or made available via links to the websites.

5.3 INFORMATION SERVICE "RESEARCH, INTERNATIONAL AFFAIRS AND TRANSFER"

The information service is an e-mail service that provides you with targeted and accurate information on research funding.

Members can register with their e-mail address and create an individual user profile. They can specify scientific fields, types of funding and sponsors about which you would like to receive information. At a time of their choice, members receive an e-mail with the current information that is important for them. If members need additional information, they can search the database at any time.

The system includes calls for proposals from the funding institutions DFG, BMBF & ministries, EU, foundations, DAAD & AvH as well as others and lists the funding

categories project funding, promotion of young researchers, prizes & competitions, international, transfer and events.

6 NETWORKING

6.1 BEYOND PEERS

The project beyond peers is a joint initiative for women from the fields of business, science, society, creative industries and politics. The aim of the initiative beyond peers is to expand your target group regionally and nationally, to increase your visibility and to grow together with others in the network.

6.2 RESEARCH CAMP

The research camp is an interdisciplinary exchange and networking platform. In an informal and familiar atmosphere, scientists from all disciplines/collaborative projects of the University of Rostock as well as the affiliated institutes present their own research topic in the popular poster session, openly offer other scientist's potential synergies for active networking and cooperation, and keep an eye out for existing contacts and new ones to be established themselves. The research camp is an important orientation point for young scientists and offers representatives of the state government and industry an opportunity to get an overview of the status of current research projects.

6.3 MARE BALTICUM FELLOWSHIP PROGRAMM

With the aim to combine the interdisciplinary guiding principle of the University of Rostock with the support of scientists in early career phases, the University of Rostock announces the MARE BALTICUM FELLOWSHIP PROGRAM annually. The fellowship program supports guest stays (max. 3 months) of national as well as international scientists*. Scientists of the University of Rostock who are members of the Interdisciplinary Faculty are eligible to apply.

On the one hand, the program is intended to provide impulses for the initiation and preparation of joint research projects. At the same time, the application is connected with the conception of a series of events for scientists in early career phases. The series of events is intended to serve the scientific examination of a superordinate topic and to facilitate an interdisciplinary and interfaculty exchange.

6.4 ROSTOCK INTERNATIONAL HOUSE

At the Rostock International House, all international exchange activities of the University of Rostock come together. It is our task to coordinate international relations and to develop and implement projects and programs with foreign partners. In addition, we provide advice and consultation for foreign students and prospective students, advices for German students who wish to study abroad and implement the ERASMUS+ program.

6.5 INTERNATIONAL MEETING CENTER

The aim of the International Meeting Center Rostock is to enable and promote scientific and cultural exchange among members of the university and other research institutions in the region, as well as the residents of the Hanseatic City of Rostock, and thus to further internationalize Rostock as a university location. The guest house is therefore more than just a place to live. For a temporary stay of 3 months to 2 years, the IBZ offers its guests comfortable living space in fully furnished apartments and a comprehensive range of support services for scientists and their families.

6.6 ENTERPRISE EUROPE NETWORK

The University of Rostock benefits together with the region through its membership in the Enterprise Europe Network. The Enterprise Europe Network supports and connects companies, universities and research institutions on issues related to innovation and internationalization, opening up foreign markets, finding business and project partners, participating in European funding programs and much more.

The Enterprise Europe Network focuses on the internationalization of small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) in industry, commerce and trade. Another focus is the promotion of cooperation and cluster formation between companies, universities and research institutions.

6.7 EU-CONEXUS

The University of Rostock is part of EU-CONEXUS. EU-CONEXUS is an association of nine European universities from France, Spain, Croatia, Romania, Greece, Lithuania, Ireland and Cyprus. The aim is to enable innovative and interdisciplinary research across national borders and to offer students a European study program. The thematic focus is on the sustainability of coastal regions.

The thematic focus is particularly relevant in view of the advancing climate change and its consequences on the increasingly densely populated coastal areas, as these regions are of crucial importance for energy production and transport, trade, aquaculture, fisheries as well as tourism.

In addition to the research and innovation dimensions, EU-CONEXUS also opens up a wide range of opportunities for students, for example European degree programs at Bachelor, Master and PhD level. Jointly, courses on different topics are offered, which can be credited at the University of Rostock.

- Minor in Coastal Development and Sustainable Maritime Tourism
- Minor in Blue Economy and Growth
- Joint Master Program in Marine Biotechnology
- PhD

7 ACADEMIA AND BUSINESS COOPERATION

7.1 URSG - TECHNOLOGY AND KNOWLEDGE TRANSFER

The URSG (University of Rostock Service GmbH) is the central internal and external service point for transfer at the University of Rostock and sees itself as a mediator between science and industry. It supports both scientists and companies in the context of technology and knowledge transfer ...

- in the initiation and coordination of joint projects,
- in the acquisition of third-party funding
- in the transfer of scientific research results into the economy as well as
- in finding adequate partners.

7.2 VVB-MV – EXPLOITATION OF RESEARCH RESULTS

From evaluation and patenting to the commercial exploitation of scientific inventions - the VVB-MV, together with its partners, supports the state's scientific institutions in all phases of the patenting and exploitation process.

In doing so, the VVB-MV is the contact point for around 3,000 scientists and also offers access to research results that are protected under patent law.

7.3 PNZ- PATENT AND STANDARD CENTER

The Patent and Standards Center (PNZ) of the Rostock University Library was opened in 1985. It provides information and services in all areas of industrial property protection. The services of the PNZ are not only available to university members, but can also be used by employees from small and medium-sized enterprises as well as by private inventors to realize innovative ideas.

7.4 CAREER SERVICE

The Careers Service supports students and graduates of the University of Rostock in planning their career entry - whether into dependent employment or self-employment. We want to enable students to discover the variety of possibilities after graduation, to formulate career goals early on and to contribute to their realization. We support graduates in making well thought-out, individually tailored decisions for their career paths and in presenting themselves convincingly to the job market in all respects.

At the same time, we are the contact address for companies wishing to recruit at the University of Rostock. We are the interface between the university and potential employers for students.

7.5 STUDENT RESEARCH PROJECTS AND THESES

Upon request and agreement, students can be given the opportunity to write their Bachelor's or Master's thesis in cooperation with a company.

8 ENTREPRENEURSHIP

The Center for Entrepreneurship is the central contact point for people interested in founding a company at the University of Rostock. The team of the center accompanies the students, graduates & scientists of the university in every phase of your start-up project - starting with the evaluation and structuring of your ideas and concepts up to the support in the formal and organizational implementation of the business start-up. The Center for Entrepreneurship advises on funding opportunities and provides support in the application process, e.g., for the EXIST-Start-up Grant, EXIST- Research Transfer. The Center for Entrepreneurship organizes various programs and events:

8.1 SEMINAR: SUCCESS FACTORS FOR PROFESSIONAL ENTREPRENEURSHIP

The sub-module I of start-up teaching "Success factors of professional self-employment" serves to generally sensitize students to the entrepreneurial perspective. Entrepreneurial action competencies are acquired that enable the innovative utilization of knowledge.

8.2 SEMINAR: IDEA GENERATION AND DEVELOPMENT

In sub-module II of the start-up teaching "Idea generation and development", students learn the theoretical and practical basics of professional self-employment, work on a problem from the business world, among other things, and develop approaches to solutions using the design thinking method.

8.3 IDEA CONTEST

A yearly idea contest supports the development of founding ideas and the utilization of research results at the University of Rostock as well as the research area Mecklenburg-Western Pomerania and increases their chances of success. Since 2016 local idea competitions are executed at participating universities and colleges in Mecklenburg-Western Pomerania, which are financed with European social funds from 2014 to 2020. Furthermore, the best submissions from the local competition qualify for the participation on the national competition. The local as well as the national competition are executed only once per year through 2019.

The "Zentrum für Entrepreneurship" (ZfE) of the University of Rostock is responsible for the execution of the local competition as well as for the coordination of the national competition. The ZfE emphasizes to integrate the majority of the research institutes in

the country into the local competition at the University of Rostock as well as to cooperate with them and to support them with the identification respectively implementation of research and transfer potential.

There will be money-awards for the first three winners in both categories and money-awards in additional certain categories, which are sponsored from various businesses. Despite this, there is a possibility for participants to attend subsequent events to work targeted on their idea respectively on the implementation.

8.4 SPINOFF INCUBATION

This program refers to the support before the formal foundation of a start-up. The services provided by SPiNOFF range from the early identification of high-potential research ideas, to the acquisition of financial resources, to the support of the company's own start-up.

Among others, the program provides information on the following topics:

- Business model according to CANVAS
- Business plan development
- Marketing strategy and sales concept
- Financial planning
- Financing of the pre-foundation phase through support programs

8.5 INCUBATOR PROGRAM

The “Incubator” program has the goal of supporting innovative and young people interested in founding their own businesses. In doing so, the program not only want to promote the regional start-up scene, but also network with each other at the same time and thus create a community among like-minded people. The target audience is interdisciplinary, coaching and programs educate on: Pitch Training, Speech Training, Clarification of Financial Terms, Marketing Basics, Self-Promotion, Social Media Consulting. In addition, support is provided in the form of technology, facilities and a prototype workshop.

8.6 ACCELERATOR PROGRAM

The accelerator program builds on the incubator program. With the "accelerator" program, the University of Rostock supports young companies, teams and individuals with promising business models to further develop their business ideas, technologies and products in a customer-centric and fast way.

The program offers innovative start-ups not only mentoring and coaching by experienced and committed experts, but also access to a large network of investors, business partners and customers. During a maximum period of nine months, the founders are also

provided with the necessary infrastructure. The program focuses on the individual needs of the participating startups, for example, to help them enter international markets, grow faster, build up a customer base faster and develop the personnel pool faster.

8.7 MVPRENEUR DAY

The MVpreneur Day is organized annually by the Center for Entrepreneurship (ZfE) of the University of Rostock, this year modified as a weekly event series in cooperation with the Digitales Innovationszentrum Rostock (DIZ) GmbH.

9 INTERDISCIPLINARY FACULTY

In the Interdisciplinary Faculty, the various scientific disciplines merge and enter into a close dialogue with each other beyond the original disciplinary boundaries. The members of the faculty drive a wide range of externally funded, coordinated and often interdisciplinary research projects.

9.1 INTERDISCIPLINARY RESEARCH PROJECTS

The members of the Department Maritime Systems drive a wide range of externally funded, coordinated and often interdisciplinary research projects.

Baltic Transcoast is a graduate program that explores the reciprocal processes between land and sea. The main goal is to train doctoral students in three-year steps to become experts of the coastal region. All research activities of the 13 ongoing doctoral theses are focused on the common research site "Heiligensee and Hütelmoor" northeast of Rostock.

Within the BACOSA (Baltic Coastal System Analysis and Status Evaluation) project, data on changes in land use pressure are compared with data on the historical ecosystem state of the German Baltic Sea coast from partners at the Universities of Rostock and Kiel. The focus is on trophic interactions, i.e. interactions in the nearshore network, and events that have a short-term effect.

More interdisciplinary ones can be found here: <https://www.inf.uni-rostock.de/en/mts/research/research-projects-and-networks/>

9.2 OCEAN TECHNOLOGY CAMPUS (OTC)

The Ocean Technology Campus is intended to strengthen German marine technology by opening up important markets and providing impetus for a worldwide knowledge-based sustainable use of the oceans. The campus with its location in Rostock's fishing port offers, on the one hand, real conditions for carrying out a wide variety of underwater tests in a specially constructed underwater test field and, on the other hand, a bundling of forces by locating companies and research institutions at the OTC.

9.3 OTC: SUMMER SCHOOL

Rostock's Ocean Technology (RoOT) Summer School is a two-week course at the end of August, which is based in and around the Ocean Technology Campus (OTC). 16 carefully chosen participants from academia and industry will have the unique opportunity to gain insight into various interdisciplinary aspects of ocean technology, with a special focus on the five fields of innovation which make up the Cluster OTC Rostock:

- Subsea Mobility & Autonomy
- Ocean Lense
- Digital Mission
- Sustainable Ocean Use
- Open Innovation

Specially tailored lectures and exercises will provide the participants with the required know-how to tackle real-world problems within various practical applications both on land and at sea (aboard Rostock's research catamaran Limanda). The program will also offer the opportunity to participate in a hackathon (with no-code/low-code options for participants that are not so familiar with coding) and to learn about advantages of open innovation, open source, networking and generally out-of-the-box thinking.

9.4 OTC: OPEN OCEAN LAB

The Ocean Open Lab (OOL) will be an open experimental workshop, a 'makerspace' dedicated to ocean technology. It doesn't matter if you are a citizen:in, a student, a graduate, an employee of a university or a company, a startup founder, a freelance inventor or a Best Ager. Everybody can come to our lab and gets free access to tools and technical equipment (e.g. 3D printer, soldering station), as well as to the necessary know-how for the realization of own marine technical ideas.

The aim of the project is to try out and establish open innovation processes as new forms of collaboration between business, science and the general public. Through a variety of event formats (hackathons, demo days, workshops, etc.), the networking of citizens with companies and research institutions is promoted.

9.5 OTC: INTERNATIONAL OCEAN ACCELERATOR

This novel accelerator program supports innovative marine and underwater technology companies in their start-up: from the idea to the growth phase.

With the International Ocean Accelerator, teams of experts from around the world are brought together to further develop start-up ideas related to marine and underwater topics.

The teams receive targeted support via the Accelerator network. They are given access to the marine technology infrastructure of the Future Cluster and can contact international experts and consortia from science and industry at any time.

The goal of the program is to enable talented individuals and their teams to realize their first projects with customers after the support period of six months, to arrange a start-up or follow-up financing round, and to aim for settlement at the Ocean Technology Campus Rostock.

**REPORTING TEMPLATE & KPIs UPDATING
CBP UAc**

KPI Description	Report Period / Date	Current status	Delivered progress	Review Actions	Responsible Department	Objective Associated to KPI	Comments
K1.1 Number of participants attending the trainings on European project writing and Science Communication					SVCT	Promote transversal skills for excellence in research	
K1.2 Number of submitted proposals to European calls					SVCT	Promote transversal skills for excellence in research	
K1.3 Number of Trainings Organized					SVCT	Promote transversal skills for excellence in research	
K1.4 Number of participants attending the trainings on Open Science good practices					SVCT	Promote transversal skills for excellence in research	
K1.5 Number of projects in the Information Platform for external funded projects					SVCT	Promote transversal skills for excellence in research	
K2.1 Number of UAc staff with training in key skills for technology transfer					InUAc	Strengthen KTT and Innovation	
K2.2 Number of KTT promoted training events					InUAc	Strengthen KTT and Innovation	
K3.1 Number of events with UAc organization / participation					ProCIED	Foster scientific education and societal involvement	
K4.1 Number of external partners trained					SCVT / InUAc	Stakeholders engagement and Internationalization	
K4.2 Number of active UAc networks					VReEGA / VReEBECI / VReAPI / VReCITC / SVCT / InUAc	Stakeholders engagement and Internationalization	
K4.3 Number of active collaborative protocols					VReEGA / VReEBECI / VReAPI / VReCITC / SVCT / InUAc	Stakeholders engagement and Internationalization	
K4.4 Number of European University Alliances participation					VReCITC	Stakeholders engagement and Internationalization	
K4.5 Number of UAc staff participating in mobility programs					ProCIED	Stakeholders engagement and Internationalization	

REPORTING TEMPLATE & KPIs UPDATING CBP ULPGC

KPI Description	Report Period / Date	Current status	Delivered progress	Review Actions	Responsible Department	Objective Associated to KPI	Comments
K1.1 Percentage of participants reporting improved competence in Research Project Management					OPE	Strengthening Research Excellence	
K1.2 Percentage of successfully submitted proposals to European calls					OPE	Strengthening Research Excellence	
K1.3 Number of Workshops Organized					VRRT, OPE	Strengthening Research Excellence	
K2.1 Number of events organized					VRRT, OPE	Fostering Responsible Research and Societal Impact	
K2.2 Number of participating educational entities (schools, high schools, etc.)					VRRT, OPE	Fostering Responsible Research and Societal Impact	
K3.1 Number of training actions delivered					VRRT, VRTAE, OPE	Developing digital and Open Science skills	
K3.2 Number of attendants to the training actions delivered					VRRT, VRTAE, OPE	Developing digital and Open Science skills	
K3.3 Percentage increase in the adoption of Open Science Practices and Data management					VRRT, UAI	Developing digital and Open Science skills	
K4.1 Number of new information sheets on technologies, knowledge and research results					OTC	Promoting Innovation and KTT	
K4.2 Social media outreach of the information campaign					OTC	Promoting Innovation and KTT	
K5.1 Number of external partners trained					OPE, OTC	Empowering Stakeholders	
K5.2 Number of training courses or workshops conducted for CIDE network technicians on R&D transfer from research organizations					OTC	Empowering Stakeholders	
K6.1 Number of projects funded by HE programme					OPE	Enhancing International collaborations	
K6.2 Number of MSCA and ERC proposals evaluated and advised by the OPE					VRRT, OPE	Enhancing International collaborations	

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